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Executive summary

This document provides an overview of the environmental control of the Mobile Test Facility. The environmental control consists of the Atmosphere Management System (AMS) and the Thermal Control System (TCS).

The Atmosphere Management System is comprised of two separate systems: The Service Section AMS which regulates the temperature and the relative humidity in the Service Section, and the FEG AMS which manages the atmosphere in the FEG via a closed-loop cycle.

The thermal subsystem of the Mobile Test Facility will remove the larger part of the heat loads produced within the facility during operations. Specifically, the thermal subsystem will provide active liquid cooling for the ISPR plant cultivation rack, the Air Management System and the LED panels and remove this heat from the facility using an externally located heat rejection unit.

The thermal system has two internal loops, to transfer heat from the aforementioned heat sources to the thermal system rack, and one external loop to transfer heat from the thermal system rack to the roof-mounted free cooler, where the heat is rejected to the external environment.

The thermal system is controlled by the ARGUS system, described in detail in the Command and Data Handling System Design Document. Three-way valves in the thermal system piping are controlled to adjust the amount of heat which is removed from the sources and rejected to the outside. The ARGUS system automatically adjusts the settings of these valves to maintain coolant temperatures within specified ranges.

This document provides an overview of the design for the Service Section AMS, the FEG AMS and the TCS along with a description of the nominal and off-nominal operations and procedures. Furthermore, an overview of the system parts and budgets is presented, along with lessons learned during the design, assembly, integration and test phases.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AMS	Air Management System	HEPA	High Efficiency Particulate Arrestance
CE	Concurrent engineering	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics	PCDS	Power Control and Distribution System
COTS	Commercial off the shelf	SS	Service Section
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	VOC	Volatile organic compound

1 Atmosphere Management System Top-level design overview

The AMS consists of two distinct systems, one closed loop for control of the FEG environment and one system for fresh air inlet into the Service Section, which ensures temperature and humidity in the Service Section stay within the set point bounds.

The top level design overview is depicted in the schematic block reported in Figure 1-1:

Figure 1-1: AMS functional schematic.

Starting from the top, the first block is the Air Circulation: this block has to provide the required amount of air flow rate at the system: main components are two fans, one before the filtration system to compensate mainly this pressure drop; the second installed after the filters on the pressure side of the ducts, to compensate the pressure drop of the duct distribution system. Furthermore, 8 circulation fans are included in this functional block, which force air circulation within the FEG. Lastly, this block covers the fan within the Service Section AMS.

The Dehumidification block shall enable the recovery of the water transpired by the plants: this water, transformed into humidity, passes through an air –liquid heat exchanger which is supplied with cooling liquid by the Thermal System. The coolant temperature and flow rate is set to reduce the air temperature below the dew point to obtain the water condensation. The subsystem ‘Recovery Water’ is composed of an UV-C lamp, Led type, a pump and a carbon filter. The filtered condensate water will be fed back to the main fresh water tank.

Heater: this block is composed of heater elements installed in a mechanical duct. After being cooled, the air has to be reheated at the proper temperature, passing through the heaters. Similarly, the Service Section AMS has a heating element to control the temperature of incoming air.

Filtration: this block is composed of a UV-C lamp, a pre-filter, an H14 HEPA filter and a VOC scrubber. The aim of this functional block is to guarantee the removal of contaminants from the air recirculating in close circuit in the greenhouse. The UV-C lamp is installed before the heat exchanger to prevent microbial build-up on the dehumidifier, but from the functional side it belongs to this block. In the Service Section AMS a pre-filter and H13 HEPA filter are incorporated into the design.

Air Distribution: This block encompasses all the components dedicated to the proper air distribution from the AMS unit to each single point of the FEG section. This system is realized with main ducts which route the air between the Service Section and the FEG. In the FEG 8 ducts are installed which route the air onto the crops, each of them with a constant flow valve and distribution louvers.

The functional block Humidification is composed of a standalone humidifier, which can be installed in the FEG if necessary to provide additional humidity to the environment. In nominal operations it is expected that a humidifier is not required in the FEG. Additionally, this functional block contains the humidifier for the Service Section AMS.

CO₂ System is the system dedicated to the maintaining of proper value of CO₂: it is composed of CO₂ bottles, control valves and distribution piping.

The control sensor system groups all the sensors foreseen in the AMS: all signals coming from those sensors will be sent to the central Argus control system.

2 Service Section AMS – Detailed design

A functional schematic for the AMS was presented previously in chapter 2. As mentioned, the AMS can be split into the FEG AMS and the Service Section AMS. The environmental conditions within the cold porch are not actively controlled, aside from a heater which maintains the temperature above a set minimum.

Within the SS, the environmental conditions are controlled through the inflow and outflow of air. In this chapter, the calculations supporting the system sizing and component selection will be presented. Margins are used to account for uncertainties within the calculations and will be indicated and justified within the text.

Figure 2-1 shows the configurations of the AMS for the Service Section. The air inlet has an H-shaped cowl, to prevent snow from entering the facility. The air enters the air duct and is first heated by a heater, before passing through a filter system. A fan ensures sufficient pressure head to overcome the losses in the system. Finally, the air enters the Service Section through the plenum and louver, with the opening located just above the door separating the cold porch and the Service Section.

A humidifier injects water vapour into the air ducts, after the fan, to maintain the relative humidity in the Service Section within the desired range.

Figure 2-1: Service Section AMS

An air outlet was initially foreseen in the design, but ultimately discarded. Because the volume flow rate for the fresh air supply is relatively low it was not deemed necessary to have a dedicated outlet. Air will leave the facility upon crew entering or exiting the facility and it is expected that this will be sufficient to prevent air pressure from rising too high, thereby preventing fresh air from entering the facility and cooling the Service Section.

2.1 System sizing/analyses

The target environmental conditions within the SS are listed below in Table 2-1. Note that the relative humidity will not be actively controlled within the SS at night. The external environmental conditions are referenced in the detailed Neumayer Station III - Exterior Environmental Conditions Summary document (EDEN ISS-DLR-WP2.1-Exterior Environmental Conditions).

Table 2-1: Target environmental conditions in the Service Section.

	Day	Night
Temperature	21°C	18°C
Relative Humidity	25-30%	N/A

To size the air management components for the Service Section environmental control, first the thermal loads need to be estimated. This is done by taking a percentage of the total power consumption of the various subsystem components within the Service Section. The power consumption values of the different subsystems, for those components which are located in the Service Section, are listed in Table 2-2, along with the percentage of the power consumption which is used to estimate the corresponding thermal load. Note that the values used for the system sizing are those power values which were available at the time of component selection and could have changed slightly. These changes have been accounted for through the use of margins on the subsystem level.

Table 2-2: Power consumption in the Service Section.

Power consumption	Day (Max)	Night (Min)	Thermal load fraction
Power Control and Distribution System	116 W	0 W	20%
Air Management System	2450 W	400 W	~0%
Thermal System	2980 W	2280 W	20%
Illumination System	0 W	0 W	N/A
Command and Data Handling System	1010 W	850 W	20%
Nutrient Delivery System	617.5 W	617.5 W	20%
Operations and Communications	0 W	0 W	N/A
ISPR	1022 W	427 W	20%
Service Section	150 W	0 W	20%
TOTAL	8345.5 W	4574.5W	N/A

The Power Control and Distribution System (PCDS) power consumption consists solely of the power consumption for general lighting. The power consumption for the external lighting, approximately 2 kW, will generate heat, but this heat will dissipate directly into the external environment. The losses and thus heat generated from other equipment within the power box itself are considered negligible.

It should be noted that the power consumption for the AMS in the SS does not yet include the heat generated by the components required for the SS environmental control. However, this heat contribution will act to increase the temperature of the incoming external air, which will reduce the actual heater power required. Furthermore, the power consumption by the emergency heater in the cold porch is not considered in these values. Despite the significant power consumption of the AMS, the thermal load introduced on the SS environment is very limited as it is, almost entirely, transported out of the MTF via a thermal cooling line, or transported into the FEG via the air. A minor thermal load is to be expected from the pump which transports the condensate water to the fresh water tank, but all the other AMS thermal loads do not impact the SS. For the thermal load estimation, a pump power consumption of 250 W is assumed and a thermal load fraction of 20%.

The thermal power consumption is a conservative estimate based on a design proposed during the CE study.

The Illumination System (IS) has no power consuming components in the SS, as the general lighting is already accounted for in the PCDS value and the LED panels for the rack-like cultivation system are accounted for in the ISPR power value.

The Command and Data Handling System (CDHS) power consumption covers the various computers, the monitors, the Argus control system and a variety of sensors and observation cameras within the Service Section.

The Nutrient Delivery System (NDS) power consumption values consist of the contributions from the non-submersed pumps (dosing pumps and main circulation pumps), sensors and the ozone generator.

The operations and communications system has no power consuming components in the SS, similar to the illumination system, as the majority of the components are located in the FEG, or externally, and the rest of the components are accounted for in the command and data handling subsystem.

For the ISPR it is assumed that 80% of the thermal load is removed via thermal cooling line, while the remaining 20% results in an increase of air temperature. The thermal load is estimated to be 20% of the power consumption of the ISPR.

The SS power consumption accounts for all non-subsystem specific components, such as speakers, and power consuming tools. The thermal loads which need to be accounted for by the air management system are listed in Table 2-3. Both the hot and cold case are indicated to give a clear overview of the maximum heating and cooling loads which need to be handled by the design. As mentioned, the thermal values presented in Table 2-3 were approximated based on SS subsystem power values available at the time of hardware acquisition for the AMS Service Section. Uncertainties were accounted for via margins on the subsystem power consumption values, as well as an additional 50% margin on the combined maximum thermal loads, as can be seen in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3: Thermal load sources in the Service Section.

Thermal Load Source	Summer Max.	Winter Min.
Power System	23.2 W	0 W
Air Management System	50 W	0 W
Thermal System	596 W	456 W
Illumination System	0 W	0 W
Command and Data Handling System	202 W	170 W
Nutrient Delivery System	125.5 W	125.5 W
Operations and Communications	0 W	0 W
ISPR	40.9 W	17.1 W
Service Section	30 W	0 W
Cold Porch	0 W	0 W
Future Exploration Greenhouse	0 W	0 W
External Environment	-383.3 W	-1706 W
TOTAL	684.3 W	-937.4 W
TOTAL with 50% margin	1026.5 W	-1406.1 W

The heat loads from the ISPR, cold porch, future exploration greenhouse and the external environment are due to temperature differentials between these sources and the internal service section environment. For the cold porch and future exploration greenhouses these are set to zero for now. The margin added to the total thermal loads will account for these contributions, as well as for the uncertainties in the other values.

The allowable temperature range within the SS is defined in the requirements document to be from 15°C to 27°C. Furthermore, the air inlet temperature is set at 5°C. The approximate volume of air in

the Service Section is ~24.67 m³ (from separation wall to separation wall ca. 4.5 x 2.15 x 2.55 m). From Table 2-3 the maximum heat load is found to be 1026.5 W.

Equation 1 can be used to estimate the volume of external air which would be needed to reduce the internal temperature from the maximum value (27°C) to the minimum value (15°C). This equation assumes the total volume remains the same, due to the air inflow and outflow rates being identical. It also assumes the extreme case of a +5°C external air temperature.

Equation 1

$$V_{in} = \frac{V_{SS} * (T_{min} - T_{max})}{(T_{in} - T_{max})} = \frac{24.67 * (15 - 27)}{(5 - 27)} \approx 13.46 m^3$$

The required humidifier capacity can be determined using Equation 2 which calculates the resultant humidity of the mixed air. The humidity in grams per kilogram of dry air can be determined from a psychrometric chart. For a wet bulb temperature of 21°C and 20% RH, the humidity is about 8.5 g/kg. In the worst case, the humidity of the external air is negligible (i.e. outside temperature is -50°C). The resultant humidity, compared with the target humidity, allows for calculation of the amount of humidity which needs to be added. With the values as described here, the resultant humidity is shown to be 3.86 g/kg, which means about 4.7 g/kg of humidity needs to be added. Note, air density is assumed to be 1.225 kg/m³.

Equation 2

$$x_{new} = \frac{V_{in} x_{in} + (V_{SS} - V_{in}) x_{SS}}{V_{SS}} = \frac{13.46 * 0 + (24.67 - 13.46) * 8.5}{24.67} \approx 3.86 \text{ g/kg}$$

Taking into account the maximum heat load stated before, the time it takes for the internal temperature to rise from the minimum to maximum allowable value is calculated using Equation 3.

Equation 3

$$t = \frac{c * V * \rho * \Delta T}{\dot{q}} = \frac{1005 * 24.67 * 1.225 * 12}{1026.5} \approx 355.1s$$

Based on the result of Equation 3, the number of partial air exchanges per hour can be determined. This, combined with the volume of external air per partial air exchange gives an initial rough estimate for the required air flow. Subsequently, the duct diameter can be calculated based on the air flow rate, taking into account that the flow velocity should be 3 m/s (Janquart, Undated; Hui, 2008) to minimize noise and duct pressure losses.

The inlet air duct heater capacity is calculated by determining the thermal load required to heat the external air from -50°C to +5°C. The Service Section heater is sized to handle the maximum heating load of 1406.1 W, as listed in Table 2-3, with some margin.

The relevant parameters and values for sizing the components, as calculated using the aforementioned calculations, can be seen in Table 2-4. Values have been rounded up.

Table 2-4: Service Section AMS design characteristics.

Component	Minimum value	Design value
Air flow rate	136.5 m ³ /h	150 m ³ /h
Inlet duct heater capacity	2567.4 W	3000 W
Humidifier capacity	785.7 g/h	1000 g/h

Service section heater capacity	1406.1 W	1500 W
Duct diameter	126.9 mm	160 mm

The system as described previously requires a fan, heater, pre-filter and a HEPA filter for the air inlet, along with a valve and valve actuator. The valve, fan and heater should be controllable via a thermostat to optimally adjust the operating set point based on the actual internal conditions. Additionally, a humidifier is required to maintain Service Section relative humidity.

2.2 Component selection

2.2.1 Air inlet valve and actuator

In order to prevent air from entering into the facility when not needed or desired, a valve will be installed near the air inlet. The VKA 160 valve, Figure 2-2, will provide an airtight seal when closed. Using a Siemens GQD321-1A actuator, the valve can be opened and shut when necessary to control the internal temperature of the Service Section.

Figure 2-2: (Left) Inlet valve. (Right) Valve actuator.

2.2.2 Duct heating element

As the external temperature can go down to $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, injecting this air directly into the Service Section could result in condensation. Therefore, the incoming air should be heated to an acceptable temperature, to prevent this.

A custom duct heating element, see Figure 2-3, has been installed in the Service Section AMS for this purpose. The heating element can provide up to 1700 W of heat into the air. A second, identical, heating element is available but has not been installed at this point, to reduce the power consumption of the MTF.

Also, it is expected that, if the external temperatures drop to such low extremes, it will not be necessary to inject external air into the facility to reduce the Service Section temperature as the heat loss to the environment will already accomplish any required cooling.

Should additional heating be necessary, the second heating element will be installed during the operations phase in the Antarctic.

Figure 2-3: Heater element.

2.2.3 Pre-filter

An F7 class pre-filter (HS-Beta Pak 85) has been installed to capture any large contaminants in the external air. While the Antarctic air is likely to be quite clean and contaminant-free, the container has also been operated in other environments which are more contaminated.

To ultimately prevent contamination in the FEG, the Service Section should also be kept as clean as possible, since crew movements are likely to transfer contaminants from one section to the next.

Figure 2-4: (Left) Pre-filter. (Right) HEPA filter.

2.2.4 HEPA filter

Similar reasoning as led to the inclusion of the pre-filter, also resulted in the inclusion of a HEPA filter, which will capture smaller contaminants not captured by the pre-filter.

The selected HEPA filter (HS-Mikro SF) is an H13 class filter with 99.95% effectiveness.

2.2.5 Fan

An estimate was made of the geometric and component-based pressure losses in the Service Section AMS, in order to select a fan which could provide sufficient pressure head to deliver the desired flow rate. Ultimately, the Iso 160-2E fan was selected in part for its performance and due to its compact size. The fan and its performance curve are shown in

Figure 2-5: (Left) Fan. (Right) Fan performance curve.

2.2.6 Humidifier

The external air in the Antarctic is extremely dry with almost negligible amounts of moisture in the air. To prevent crew health issues from developing as a result of constant movement between the dry external environment and a moist internal environment, the Service Section will operate at a low relative humidity of between 20 and 30%. Nevertheless, when external air is brought into the facility it is possible that the relative humidity could drop below even these low set points.

As such a small humidifier (the Airwin UB-1 ultrasonic air humidifier) with a capacity of 0.5 kg/h has been installed into the Service Section AMS. The capacity of this humidifier is lower than the value previously calculated as it is expected that there will be a significant amount of air exchange between the Service Section and the FEG when crew are inside, which will result in additional humidity entering into the Service Section atmosphere.

Figure 2-6: Humidifier.

2.3 Options and trades

During the Concurrent Engineering study carried out in September 2015, at DLR Bremen, two options were considered for the Service Section air inlet architecture:

Option 1: Environmental control using only external air.

Option 2: Environmental control using recirculated internal air, with minimal external air.

Preliminary configurations for both options are shown in Figure 2-7 and Figure 2-8.

Figure 2-7: Preliminary layout for option 1.

Figure 2-8: Preliminary layout for option 2.

Table 2-5 has an overview of the relevant characteristics of the two options. It should be noted that these values are based on calculations done during the CE study, with the values available at that time.

For option 1 three different scenarios were considered, each with a different air inlet and air outlet temperature. Based on the air inlet temperature the air flow rate required to handle the SS heat load was determined. Furthermore, the heating power necessary to heat the incoming air from the external temperature to the selected inlet temperature was determined.

From the flow rate, the humidifier capacity could be sized and the duct diameter (wall opening diameter) could be determined, by targeting a flow velocity of 3 m/s within the ducts.

Option 2 aims to reduce the amount of air flowing into the facility from the outside, by recirculating the internal air. The heat load would be transported out of the facility using a liquid-air heat ex-

changer connected to a heat rejection unit on the roof of the MTF. This design would require a more powerful pump for the thermal system, as well as a larger heat rejection unit, but would reduce the amount of power required to heat the external air flowing into the facility.

Table 2-5: Comparison table for design option 1 and 2.

	DeltaT	Ext. Air Flow Rate		Int. Air Flow Rate	Heaters Power		Humidifier	Wall Opening	Complexity
		max	min		min	max			
	°C	m ³ /h	m ³ /h	m ³ /h	W	W	kg/h	mm	Min 1
Option 1	16-26	500	167	Same of ext.	1.600	3.800	0,8	240	1
	12-27	338	110	Same of ext.	680	2.360	0,5	200	1
	10-28	280	90	Same of ext.	400	1.600	0,4	180	1
Option 2	18-27	30	30	700	0	550	0,2	60	3

As can be seen in Table 2-5 (note that the values presented are out-of-date but that the summary table remains a useful comparative summary of the solution options), the drawbacks of option 1 are the power supply, the increased humidifier capacity, and the larger opening in the wall. However, this solution avoids the complexity of an added air-water heat exchanger and likely will be cheaper and require less volume as well.

As such, option 1 was selected as the baseline design for the Service Section air inlet architecture.

2.4 Subsystem key values

The AMS budgets are shown in Table 2-6. The spare components which will be taken along for the Antarctic campaign are also incorporated in the table, along with consumables, such as filters. Note that the water required for the humidifiers is not included here.

Also note that the peak power is the (maximum) installed power, but this value does not include the 1500 W Service Section heater. It was decided that this function could be met by the emergency heater in the Service Section. This component has already been accounted for and could thus be removed from this subsystem budget.

The mass of the ducting and the filter casing was estimated to be 20 kg.

Table 2-6: Key values of the Service Section AMS.

	Mass	Peak power
Mobile Test Facility	40.2 kg	2070 W
Spares, consumables, tools	21.5 kg	N/A
TOTAL	61.7 kg	2070 W

3 AMS Service Section Operations

3.1 Nominal operations

3.1.1 Automatic actions

- Measure Service Section temperature and relative humidity
- Measure external temperature
- Control actuator to open valve if temperature exceeds upper set point
- Turn power to fan on if temperature exceeds upper set point
- Turn power to heater(s) on
 - o Power should be linearly scaled from 0% to 100% with decreasing external temperature (from 5 degrees to -20 degrees)
- Turn humidifier on if relative humidity drops below set point
- Turn humidifier off if relative humidity reaches set point level
- Turn power to heater(s) off if temperature drops below set point
 - o Note: most likely heaters should be turned off slightly earlier and air flow should continue to enable residual heat from the heaters to be transferred into Service Section.
- Turn fan off if temperature drops below set point
 - o Note: Wait 30 (TBC) seconds after turning heaters off, before turning the fan off.
- Control actuator to shut valve.

- If temperature drops below lower set point, turn SS emergency heater on.

3.1.2 Operator actions

- Periodically (weekly or monthly) initiate the flushing / self-cleaning cycle of the humidifier
- Remove humidifier (monthly or bi-monthly) for a manual cleaning procedure
- Inspect ducts and clean them / spray them with a cleaning agent on a weekly basis
- Replace filters every six months.

3.2 Off-Nominal operations

3.2.1 Automatic actions

- Provide warning if AMS SS temperature falls outside of set point range
- Provide warning if AMS relative humidity falls outside of set point range

3.2.2 Operator actions

- In case of relative humidity notification, inspect the humidifier and connected piping and ducting
- In case temperature is too low, inspect the emergency heater
- In case temperature is too high, check fresh air inlet grate for air flow
 - o If no airflow can be detected, check valve actuator and replace actuator if damaged. Check the filters and replace them if they are clogged. Check the fan and replace the fan if damaged
 - o If airflow can be detected, check power supply to heating elements

3.3 Maintenance and spares

- Filter replacement every ~6 months
 - o HEPA filter and pre-filter spares required

- Fan replacement N/A
 - o In case of failure, a replacement fan needs to be installed

- Valve actuator replacement N/A

- In case of failure, a replacement actuator needs to be installed
- Humidifier replacement N/A
 - In case of failure, a replacement humidifier needs to be installed
- Duct cleaning / disinfection weekly (TBC)
 - Periodic cleaning of duct outlet, and spraying with Mikrozyd / cleaning agent
- Humidifier flushing / self-cleaning cycle activation weekly (TBC)
 - Manually initialize the flushing cycle of the humidifier
- Humidifier cleaning monthly / bi-monthly
 - Disconnect and remove humidifier
 - Open humidifier and manually clean tank and transducers
 - Clean humidifier fan filter

3.4 Preparation for shipment

3.4.1 Disassembly and pre-shipment preparation

- Removal of externally mounted components (H-shaped cowl)
- Close air flow valve and fix position
- Flush and clean the humidifier
- Remove filters

3.4.2 In-situ assembly and pre-operation setup

- Clean ducts and spray Mikrozyd / disinfection agent
- Install externally mounted components
- Install new pre- and HEPA filters
- Initiate humidifier flushing cycle
- Turn emergency heater on until Service Section air temperature reaches nominal set point
- Turn humidifier on until Service Section air relative humidity reaches nominal set point

4 Future Exploration Greenhouse AMS - Detailed design

The FEG AMS is a closed-loop system, located in the Service Section rack, which monitors and controls the atmospheric conditions within the FEG. This chapter provides a detailed overview of the design of this system, including, among others, the sizing calculations and the component selection.

4.1 Detailed Block diagram(s)

The figure below shows in detail the content of each functional block of the FEG AMS

Figure 4-1: Detailed AMS subassembly block diagram.

The figures below show a physical general overview of the AMS. Figure 4-2 describes the parts located in the Service Section and Figure 4-3 depicts the part located in the FEG, while Figure 4-4 shows the complete system, excluding the CO₂ storage and distribution. The main part of the CO₂ system is depicted in Figure 4-5, which shows the externally-mounted bottles and distribution panels.

Figure 4-2: AMS parts located in Service Section.

Figure 4-3: AMS parts located in FEG.

Figure 4-4: AMS assembly.

Figure 4-5: CO2 bottles and distribution panels.

4.2 System sizing/analyses

This chapter will report the description of each functional block and the main calculations and analysis used in the sizing of the various components of the system.

4.2.1 AMS baseline Design

The following aspects of the atmosphere management system will be discussed here:

- Air flow rate for FEG and SS
- Air inlet and outlet temperature
- Relative humidity
- Filtration and cleaning, with control and removal of VOC and dirt
- Control of O₂ and CO₂
- Air distribution in FEG and SS

The following values and assumptions are used as basis for the calculations.

Crop parameters:

- Production area 12,3 m²
- Transpiration rate: Day, 160 g/m²h (total: 2050 g/h - all trays, fully mature crops) Night, 385 g/h
- CO₂ requirements – 370 g/day (actual calculated)
- ppEthylene_{max} = 15 ppb (continuous), 100 ppb (trans. – 30 min)
- Canopy level wind speed: 0,4 m/sec preferable (long term) max wind speed 5 m/s for few hours min. wind speed 0.01 m/s

FEG internal parameters:

- Tnom = 22°C, Tmax = 30°C for one day with light; Tmax = 34°C, Tmin = 8°C for 2 days
- RH = 70±5%, RHmin = 45% for 12 hours
- RHmax = 96% for 4 hours (assumed the distribution throughout the FEG is perfect)
- ppCO₂ = 650 ppm, ppCO₂ max = 1500 ppm (24 hours) (germination phase & cucumber is limiting)
- Leakage: 500% total FEG volumes per day (note that this considers leakage from the FEG – not the MTF overall).
- LED power: 4,5 kW

External environmental parameters:

- Summer: +5°C, max. temperature, with RH of 92% ref.
- Winter: -50°C, min. temperature, humidity negligible
- Solar radiation: min. 0 W/m² max. 960 W/m²

4.2.2 Thermal Load Calculation

The internal air flow rate will be defined based mainly on a comparison of two factors:

- Thermal gradient of the air, function of the thermal load to be dissipated
- Number of air exchanges required by the crop

In order to establish an air flow rate enable to maintain a stated temperature gradient, the thermal load inside the MTF has to be known. The following tables summarize the results of the thermal load calculation:

Note: The numbers used in the calculations in this chapter are those which were available at the time of the system sizing. The numbers have changed over the course of the facility design, but through the inclusion of margins early on, these changes have been pre-emptively accommodated.

Table 4-1: Thermal Loads- Sensible heat.

	SENSIBLE HEAT	Light Period(W)	Dark Period (W)
ILS	ILLUMINATION SYSTEM- tot. 4.800 W		
	35% heating in the air	1700	0
	20% of 65% cooled by liquid	700	0
NDS		0	0
AMS	Heated dissipated in air by AMS unit	400 ¹	400
TCS		0	0
	Total	2.800	400

¹Note: Main heat dissipation comes from the two fans. Maximum power of each of the fans is 750 W. The ≈ 80% of two fans power goes directly into the flow rate as heating. The remaining 20% will be dissipated in air, so 150 W each for a total of 300 W. The two fans will be powered on 24 hours a day because the air has to circulate continuously: it will be possible to select a reduced flow rate during the night hours.

Table 4-2: Thermal Loads- Latent heat.

CROP	LATENT HEAT	16 h	8h
1*	Daily Water production	160 gr/m ² .h	30 gr/m ² .h
2*	Crop Surface	12,3 m ²	12,3 m ²
3*	Water production per hour	2050 gr/h	385 gr/h
4*	Vaporization heating	540 cal/gr	540 cal/gr
5*	Conversion factor cal/h – W	1 W= 860 cal/h	1 W= 860 cal/h
	Total = (3* x 4* / 5*)	1.250 W	240 W

Table 4-3: Thermal Balance with External loads.

Heat Source	Light		Dark	
	Summer (W)	Winter (W)	Summer (W)	Winter (W)
Conduction Heat (k= 0,4W/m ² K)	-387	-1.640	-387	-1.640
Solar Radiation	160	0	160	0
Internal Heat	2.800	2.800	400	400
Total Sensible Heat	2.573	1.160	173	-1.240
Crop Initial Balance	2.573	1.160	173	-1.240
Latent Heat	-1.250	-1.250	-240	-240
Crop Mature Balance	1.323	-90	-67	-1.480

From the tables above, the maximum cooling and heating requirements can be determined, by reading the maximum positive and negative total (crop initial or crop mature balance) values.

Max. cooling requirements: 1323 W

Max. heating requirements: 1480 W

Note that the crop mature balance of 1323 W will be used here instead of the crop initial balance of 2573 W. The inclusion of a humidifier in the start-up phase of the FEG will provide at least the same cooling load as will be provided by evapotranspiration of the plants later in their growth cycle.

Air Flow Rate estimation

For the air flow rate estimation, the maximum cooling requirement is used.

Based on discussions with horticulture experts, an acceptable temperature gradient for the FEG was determined to be roughly 3°C. From the heat load and the allowable temperature gradient, the flow rate is estimated as follows:

$$V = \frac{1323 * 0.86}{3 * 0.24 * 1.2} = 1317 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$$

Where : 0,86 is the conversion factor 1 W = 0,860 Kcal/h

0,24 is the specific heat of air, at constant pressure, in kcal/h x kg

1,2 is the air density in kg/m³

In commercial greenhouses, generally the number of volume air exchanges is assumed to be 1/min. For the FEG volume of approximately 31 m³ this would result in a required flow rate of 1860 m³/h.

Considering the small volume of the FEG, the first flow rate estimation method will be used as a sizing tool. The target nominal flow rate is set at 1400 m³/h, which corresponds to 1680 kg/h at 22°C.

Starting from this flow rate of 1400 m³/h, the temperature gradient is calculated to be ~2.8 °C.

Internal balance temperature and RH:

Based on the calculated temperature gradient, the known transpiration rate and the desired conditions within the FEG, the air inlet and outlet conditions can be determined.

Nominal set point conditions in the FEG are: 22°C with RH= 70 ± 5 %

From this the air inlet conditions are taken to be:

- Air inlet conditions: 20,5°C with relative humidity of 70%

Note: The air inlet temperature is the nominal temperature minus roughly half of the expected temperature gradient. The selected air inlet conditions result in a water content of 10,58 g/kg and a specific weight of 1,2 kg/m³

- Air outlet temperature = 20,5 + 2,8 = 23,3 °C

The transpiration rate (assuming day time conditions) is 2050 g/h. With an air mass flow rate of 1680 kg/h this leads to an increase of water content of:

- Water content increase = 2050 g/h / 1680 kg/h = 1,22 g/kg

The total water content becomes 11,8 g/kg, which, at a temperature of 23,3 °C corresponds to a relative humidity of ~65%. Thus, the air outlet conditions become:

- Air outlet conditions: 23,3°C with RH= 65%

Verification of air transformations with a Mollier diagram

The entire closed loop cycle of the air entering the FEG, exiting the FEG and being treated prior to re-entry into the FEG was modelled with the software “Psychrometric Analysis Design Suite” version 7.5.0. For each process the screen of the program is shown, depicting the starting conditions, the process parameters and the current conditions (at the end of the process).

The following parameters are shown in each of the process screens:

Parameter	Physical meaning	Unit
Air flow	Air mass flow rate	Kg/h
DB	Dry bulb temperature	°C
WB	Wet bulb temperature	°C
RH	Relative humidity	%
W	Water content	g/kg
v	Specific volume	m ³ /kg
h	Enthalpy	kJ/kg
DP	Dew point temperature	°C
d	Density	Kg/m ³
vp	Vapour pressure	mmHG
AW	Absolute humidity	g/m ³
	Total Cooling	W
	Total Energy	W
	Sensible Energy	W
	Latent Energy	W
	Dehumidification	Kg/h
	Sensible heat ratio	-
	Enthalpy/humidity ratio	(kJ/kg) / (g/kg)

As mentioned previously, the conditions of the air entering the FEG are 20,5°C with RH 70%. These conditions are entered as starting point conditions for the model.

Process		Current Point	
Add State Point		DB	20,500
		RH	70,00000
		Air Flow	1.680,0
		DB	20,500
		WB	16,887
		RH	70,00
		W	10,58
		v	0,846
		h	47,398
		DP	14,844
		d	1,1950
		vp	12,6643
AW	12,515		

After the inlet, the air will be heated to model the effect of the FEG thermal loads. Note that the latent heat is modelled in a separate process and as such the applied heat load in this step is 2.573 W.

As shown below, the application of thermal loads (excluding the latent heat) results in a temperature increase to 25.8 °C.

Start Point	Process	Current Point
FEG inlet	Connect State Points	DB 25,800
		W 10,58000
Air Flow 1.680,0	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy 2.529	Air Flow 1.680,0
DB 20,500	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy 2.533	DB 25,800
WB 16,887	<input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy -5	WB 18,667
RH 70,00	<input type="checkbox"/> Moisture Difference 0,0	RH 50,78
W 10,58	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio 1,002	W 10,58
v 0,846	<input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio -1.394,247	v 0,861
h 47,398		h 52,818
DP 14,844		DP 14,839
d 1,1950		d 1,1738
vp 12,6643		vp 12,6598
AW 12,515		AW 12,289

The second process step is the simulation of plant transpiration via latent heat and an addition of moisture into the system. The transpiration of the plants causes an increase of humidity and a decrease of temperature, as shown in the figure below. The conditions at the end of the process reflect the conditions of the air leaving the FEG.

Start Point		Process		Current Point	
Thermal Load		Cooling Coil		DB	23,150
				W	11,65000
Air Flow	1.680,0	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Cooling	0,003	Air Flow	1.680,0
DB	25,800	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy	3	DB	23,150
WB	18,667	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy	-1.269	WB	18,642
RH	50,78	<input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy	1.272	RH	65,42
W	10,58	<input type="checkbox"/> Dehumidification	1,8	W	11,65
v	0,861	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio	-393,818	v	0,855
h	52,818	<input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio	-0,011	h	52,825
DP	14,839			DP	16,317
d	1,1738			d	1,1835
vp	12,6598			vp	13,9179
AW	12,289			AW	13,629

The conditions of the air at the outlet of the FEG are: 23,15 °C and 65,4 % of RH. This air will enter the FEG AMS system, where it will first pass through the dehumidifier, where water will be recovered by condensation. The target end condition of this process is to reduce the water content (W) to 10,58 g/kg, which is the water content which was present in the starting air conditions.

The process screen below indicates the amount of cooling which needs to be provided by the dehumidifier in order to reach the desired amount of dehumidification.

Start Point		Process		Current Point	
Plant transp.		Cooling Coil		DB	16,000
				W	10,58000
Air Flow	1.680,0	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Cooling	-4,688	Air Flow	1.680,0
DB	23,150	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy	-4.688	DB	16,000
WB	18,642	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy	-3.418	WB	15,272
RH	65,42	<input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy	-1.270	RH	92,83
W	11,65	<input type="checkbox"/> Dehumidification	-1,8	W	10,58
v	0,855	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio	0,729	v	0,833
h	52,825	<input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio	9,372	h	42,777
DP	16,317			DP	14,839
d	1,1835			d	1,2136
vp	13,9179			vp	12,6598
AW	13,629			AW	12,705

At the outlet of the dehumidifier, the air will be at 16°C with 92% of RH. Before being reintroduced in the FEG, the air needs to be reheated to 20,5°C in order to attain the initial starting conditions. The amount of heat which needs to be added to reach this temperature is found from the process screen below to be 2151 W.

Start Point		Process		Current Point	
Dehumidif.		Connect State Points		DB	20,500
				W	10,58000
Air Flow	1.680,0	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy	2.151	Air Flow	1.680,0
DB	16,000	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy	2.151	DB	20,500
WB	15,272	<input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy	0	WB	16,883
RH	92,83	<input type="checkbox"/> Moisture Difference	0,0	RH	69,97
W	10,58	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio	1,000	W	10,58
v	0,833	<input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio	-664.406.945	v	0,846
h	42,777			h	47,388
DP	14,839			DP	14,839
d	1,2136			d	1,1950
vp	12,6598			vp	12,6598
AW	12,705			AW	12,510

The different processes described above are represented graphically in the Mollier Diagram below.

Figure 4-6: Air Transformation on Mollier Diagram.

The energy balance of this cycle is presented in the table below.

ENERGY BALANCE OF THE TRANSFORMATION

heating calculated in thermal balance	+ 2533 W
plant transpiration	-1269 W latent + 1272 W sensible
dehumidification	- 4688 w (- 3418 sensible - 1270 latent)
electrical heating	+2151 W
Total	0

CONDENSATION RISK:

Examining the dew points for the different processes we find the highest dew point to be: 16,3°C. If the relative humidity at the start is higher, the dew point and the risk of condensation will naturally be different. For example, for air at 23,2°C with 80% RH the dew point temperature is 19,5°C.

AMS Air Treatment – Coldest Case Winter & Dark Period

For the modelling of the cold case, the following starting conditions are used: 18°C with 70% of RH.

Process		Current Point	
Add State Point		DB	18,000
		RH	70,00000
		Air Flow	1.680,0
		DB	18,000
		WB	14,626
		RH	70,00
		W	9,03
		v	0,836
		h	40,910
		DP	12,450
		d	1,2063
		vp	10,8366
		AW	10,801

As before, the following process steps were performed:

- Application of the heat load (excluding latent heat)
- Application of latent heat and introduction of transpired moisture
- Dehumidification
- Heating

During this scenario the MTF will lose heat to the external environment. A loss of heat of 1045 W was applied during this process. Note the discrepancy with the value listed in the tables earlier in this chapter. A small error was found which resulted in a change of the expected heat loss. However, as the change was minor and the component selection was not impacted it was deemed unnecessary to re-run the simulation. The four process screens related to the aforementioned steps are shown below.

Start Point	Process	Current Point
FEG inlet Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 18,000 WB 14,626 RH 70,00 W 9,03 v 0,836 h 40,910 DP 12,450 d 1,2063 vp 10,8366 AW 10,801	Cooling Coil <input type="checkbox"/> Total Cooling -1,045 <input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy -1,045 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy -1,039 <input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy -6 <input type="checkbox"/> Dehumidification 0,0 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio 0,995 <input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio 481,787	DB 15,820 W 9,03000 Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 15,820 WB 13,788 RH 80,35 W 9,03 v 0,830 h 38,671 DP 12,444 d 1,2154 vp 10,8326 AW 10,877

Start Point	Process	Current Point
Thermal load Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 15,820 WB 13,788 RH 80,35 W 9,03 v 0,830 h 38,671 DP 12,444 d 1,2154 vp 10,8326 AW 10,877	Connect State Points <input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy 0 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy -272 <input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy 272 <input type="checkbox"/> Moisture Difference 0,4 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio 928,000 <input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio -0,020	DB 15,250 W 9,26000 Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 15,250 WB 13,782 RH 85,43 W 9,26 v 0,829 h 38,670 DP 12,822 d 1,2177 vp 11,1045 AW 11,172

Start Point	Process	Current Point
Plant transp. Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 15,250 WB 13,782 RH 85,43 W 9,26 v 0,829 h 38,670 DP 12,822 d 1,2177 vp 11,1045 AW 11,172	Cooling Coil <input type="checkbox"/> Total Cooling -1,344 <input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy -1,344 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy -1,073 <input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy -271 <input type="checkbox"/> Dehumidification -0,4 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio 0,798 <input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/ Humidity Ratio 12,505	DB 13,000 W 9,03000 Air Flow 1.680,0 DB 13,000 WB 12,671 RH 96,43 W 9,03 v 0,822 h 35,790 DP 12,444 d 1,2274 vp 10,8326 AW 10,984

Start Point		Process		Current Point	
Dehumidif.		Connect State Points		DB	18,000
				W	9,03000
Air Flow	1.680,0	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy	2,383	Air Flow	1.680,0
DB	13,000	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy	2,383	DB	18,000
WB	12,671	<input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy	0	WB	14,622
RH	96,43	<input type="checkbox"/> Moisture Difference	0,0	RH	69,96
W	9,03	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio	1,000	W	9,03
v	0,822	<input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/Humidity Ratio	-736.153.500	v	0,836
h	35,790			h	40,898
DP	12,444			DP	12,444
d	1,2274			d	1,2063
vp	10,8326			vp	10,8326
AW	10,984			AW	10,796

The process cycle is graphically depicted in the Mollier diagram below

Figure 4-7: Air Transformation on Mollier Diagram- Coldest Case.

The highest dew point temperature (12,5°C) observed from the process screens occurs at the FEG outlet when the air conditions are 18°C with 70% relative humidity.

CONCLUSIONS

From modelling the two extreme scenarios, the following conclusions can be drawn with regard to component sizing:

- The fans should be selected to provide a volume air flow rate of 1400 m³/h
- Total thermal capability of the dehumidifier, sensible + latent, should be 4488 W. A nominal capacity of 5000 W should be targeted.

- Heaters capability should be at least 2151 W in the hot period, and 2383 W in the cold period. Design capability should be 3000 W
- Humidifier capability: 2050 g/h minimum when the plants are not yet mature. The nominal capacity should be 3000 g/h.

4.2.3 Air circulation – Fans selection

The fan selection driving parameters are:

- Performances: flow rate versus pressure curve (the total pressure of two fans in series is the sum of the single pressure)
- Temperature range: functional and storage-transport
- Suitable shape for the application, and
- Construction materials

A simulation was done of the geometric and component-based pressure losses, which is described in the CFD Simulations Report. The main results are summarized below.

Table 4-4: AMS Geometric Pressure Drop (Reference ES calculations).

Table 4-5: AMS Geometric Pressure Drop.

Component	Delta P [Pa]	Total
filter hepa	649	2035
filter voc	217	
dehumidifier	163	
heater	1.4	
filter out	109	
equivalent circuit	458	
prefilter	65	
goemetric loss	373	
fan1	1013	2035
fan2	1022	

The proposed fan model is the K3G 250-AT39-74 manufactured by Ebmpapst. Considering the pressure capability of two fans on curve B, see Figure 4-9, the delivery flow rate will be 1458 m³/h.

Figure 4-8: Analysis Results (Reference ES calculations).

During the test it has been verified that the required flow rate of 1400 m³/h can be obtained with the fans powered at 70%. With the fans at 100% the flow rate was 1600 m³/h. This result is consistent with the calculations because during the tests the filter are cleaned, so the total pressure drop was about 300 Pa lower than the maximum, 700 Pa instead of 1000 Pa. See blue line on graphic Figure 4-9.

Figure 4-9: Fan K3G 250-AT39 -74 Performance curves.

EC centrifugal fans – RadiPac

backward curved, Ø 250

- **Material:** Support bracket: Steel, coated in black
Support plate and inlet nozzle: Sheet steel, galvanised
Impeller: Sheet aluminium
Rotor: Coated in black
Electronics enclosure: Die-cast aluminium
- **Number of blades:** 7
- **Direction of rotation:** Clockwise, seen on rotor
- **Type of protection:** IP 54 (acc. to EN 60529)
- **Insulation class:** "B"
- **Mounting position:** Shaft horizontal or rotor on bottom; rotor on top on request
- **Condensate discharges:** Rotor-side
- **Mode of operation:** Continuous operation (S1)
- **Bearings:** Maintenance-free ball bearings

Nominal data		Curve	Nominal voltage range	Frequency	Speed/rpm ⁽¹⁾	Max. input power ⁽¹⁾	Max. current draw ⁽¹⁾	Perm. amb. temp.	Technical features and electr. connection
Type	Motor	VAC	Hz	rpm	W	A	°C		
*3G 250	M3G 084-DF	A	1~ 200-277	50/60	3000	448	2,80	-25..+40	p. 88 / K1
*3G 250	M3G 084-FA	B	1~ 200-277	50/60	3450	750	3,30	-25..+40	p. 91 / L7

Technical description	
Mass	9 kg
Size	250 mm
Surface of rotor	Coated in black
Material of electronics housing	Die-cast aluminium, coated in black
Material of impeller	Aluminium sheet, white plastic-coated
Material of mounting plate	Sheet steel, galvanised and coated in white
Material of support bracket	Steel, galvanised and coated in black
Material of inlet nozzle	Sheet steel, galvanised and coated in white
Number of blades	7
Direction of rotation	Clockwise, seen on rotor
Type of protection	IP 54
Insulation class	"B"
Humidity (F)/environmental protection class (H)	F5
Max. permissible ambient motor temp. (transp./ storage)	+80 °C
Min. permissible ambient motor temp. (transp./storage)	-40 °C
Mounting position	Shaft horizontal or rotor on bottom; rotor on top on request
Condensate discharge holes	Rotor-side
Cooling bore / aperture	On rotor sides
Operation mode	S1
Motor bearing	Ball bearing
Technical features	- Output 10 VDC, max. 1.1 mA - Alarm relay - Motor current limit - Soft start - Control input 0-10 VDC / PWM - Control interface with SELV potential safely disconnected from the mains - Over-temperature protected electronics / motor - Line undervoltage detection
EMC interference immunity	Acc. to EN 61000-6-2 (industrial environment)
EMC interference emission	Acc. to EN 61000-6-3 (household environment)
Touch current acc. IEC 60990 (measuring network Fig. 4, TN system)	<= 3,5 mA
Motor protection	Thermal overload protector (TOP) wired internally
Cable exit	Variable
Protection class	I (if protective earth is connected by customer)
Product conforming to standard	EN 61800-5-1 / CE
Approval	UL 2111 / EAC / CSA C22.2 No.77

Figure 4-10: Fan technical characteristics.

The power consumed by each fan, with new filters, is 560 W per fan, for a total of 1120 W for both fans. This value can increase up to 1400 W when the filters are clogged and the fans are required to provide more pressure head.

4.2.4 Dehumidification

The dehumidification function is done by an air-liquid heat exchanger: the air is the flow rate coming from the FEG and the cooling liquid is supplied by the thermal control. In order to obtain the maximum condensation of water, the temperature of the cold surface of the heat exchanger shall be the closest as possible to the dew point of the air: stating the air conditions at T= 23,5 °C and RH = 65,5 % the dew point will be 16,7 °C .

As cooling fluid a mixture of 40% water with 60% propylene glycol was considered for the initial dehumidifier sizing, very similar for the thermal characteristics of Tyfocor (Tyfocor is a mixture of propylene glycol).The inlet temperature of the cooling fluid was stated at 8°C . A preliminary estimation of the flow rate can be done considering a desirable delta T of the cooling fluid of about 5-8°C. The specific heat of the mixture with Tyfocor at 60%, suitable for -40°C, is about 3 kJ/kg*K, as shown in the table below:

Table 4-6: Tyfocor Heat Capacity.

T [°C]	25 % vol.	30 % vol.	35 % vol.	40 % vol.	45 % vol.	50 % vol.	55 % vol.	60 % vol.
120	4.152	4.138	4.085	4.022	3.949	3.866	3.753	3.641
110	4.132	4.108	4.055	3.982	3.909	3.816	3.714	3.601
100	4.112	4.078	4.015	3.952	3.869	3.776	3.674	3.562
90	4.082	4.048	3.985	3.912	3.830	3.737	3.634	3.522
80	4.062	4.019	3.955	3.883	3.790	3.697	3.595	3.483
70	4.032	3.989	3.916	3.843	3.750	3.658	3.555	3.443
60	4.012	3.959	3.886	3.803	3.710	3.608	3.506	3.403
50	3.982	3.919	3.846	3.763	3.671	3.568	3.466	3.364
40	3.962	3.889	3.816	3.734	3.631	3.529	3.426	3.324
30	3.933	3.859	3.776	3.694	3.591	3.489	3.387	3.285
20	3.913	3.830	3.747	3.654	3.552	3.449	3.347	3.245
10	3.883	3.790	3.707	3.615	3.512	3.400	3.308	3.206
0	3.863	3.760	3.677	3.585	3.472	3.360	3.268	3.166
-10	3.833	3.730	3.637	3.545	3.433	3.321	3.219	3.126
-20	-	-	-	3.505	3.393	3.281	3.179	3.087
-30	-	-	-	-	-	3.241	3.139	3.048
-40	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.100	3.008
-50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.966

So, the flow rate P of the cooling fluid is given by this formula:

$$P = Q (\text{heat to dissipate}) / \Delta T \times \text{Heat Cap.} = 5 / (5 \times 3) = 0,33 \text{ kg/sec} = 1.188 \text{ kg/h}$$

The dimensioning of the heat exchanger, has been performed with the flow rate of cooling fluid equal to 1082 l/h with an inlet temperature of 8°C and an outlet of 12,9°C (delta T 4,9°C) and the heat capacity is 5,13 kW, with a safety factor of 10%.

The dimensions are 400 x 350 height x 200 mm depth, 8 rows.

Utilizing the software package REcalc- Ver.1.2.37, it was verified the size of the heat exchanger and the performances for the dehumidification purpose.

The condensed water is 0,59 g/sec, 2,2 l/h, (the minimum required value was 2 l/h).

The materials are copper tube with aluminum fins: the cooling fluid is compatible with the copper.

In order to guarantee the external protection a surface treatment of Ecofen (commercial name: Heresite, heat cured phenolic) can be adopted, It is very resistant against the salt spray and the erosion activated by the air flow through the fins. Note: the resistance against salt spray, measured in hours, is a way to measure the quality and reliability of a heat exchanger.

Table 4-7: Heat Exchanger performance data.

Cooling Coil Longoni Engineering code	Inox304-Al-Inox304 P40AR 4R-8T-400°-2.5pa 2C ¾"
Tune Material	Inox 304 16,45 x 0,60 mm
Fin Material	Al 0,20 mm
Frame	Inox 304 2 mm
Ext. Surface	12,57 m ²
Weight	20 Kg
Max pressure	21 Bar
Temp. Min / Temp. Max	-20°C / +100°C
Certificate	PED 97/23/CE Art. 3.3
External Gas	Air Std / 101,32 kPa
Flow Rate	1400 m ³ /h - 0,39 m ³ /sec – 0,47 kg/sec
Velocity	3,13 m/sec
Inlet and Outlet Temperature	23,50 °C – 16,06°C
Inlet and Outlet Relative Humidity	65,5 % - 93,54%
Inlet and Outlet Water content	
Condensed Water	2,1 kg/h
Sensible Heat Factor	0,70
Pressure Drop	180 Pa
Internal Fluid	Water 80% - Prop. Glic. 20%
Flow Rate	1188 kg/h
Velocity	0,87 m/sec
Inlet and Outlet Temperature	8 °C – 12,06°C
Pressure Drop	15,20 kPa
Spec. Heat	3773,48 J/kgK
Spec. Weight	1033 kg/ m ³
Viscosity	2,63 mPa.s
Conductivity	0,49 W/mK
Capacity	5,05 kW Counter Flow
Safety Factor	10%

Figure 4-11: Heat Exchanger installed in SS.

The below figure 4-12 shows the installation of the dehumidifier: on the bottom part of the exchanger is located a tank, where the condensed water will be collected.

1	Heat Exchanger
2	Purge valve
3	Drop water separator
4	Water Condensed Tank
5	Visual Level Indicator
6	Level Switch
7	Pump
8	UV-C Lamp
9	Carbon Filter

Figure 4-12: Dehumidifier and water condensed piping.

UV-C light

The selected model of UV-C lamp is the PearlAqua 6D, shown in Fig.4-13:

Figure 4-13: UV-C lamp for water disinfection.

The water to be treated has a maximum flow rate of 2,1 l/h, 0,035 l/min

The maximum flow rate declared by the data sheet of this lamp is 1,8 l/min, so the ratio with the flow rate of the unit is ~ 50. The declared value of UV-C dose is 40 mJ/cm², referred to NSF 55 Class A requirement. Class A systems are designed with warning devices and/or automatic shutoffs that activate when UV light dosage reaches a fail-safe point below 40 mJ/cm². The automatic shutoff is the preferred installation in order to avoid the consumption of untreated water.

The positive ratio between the flow rate foreseen for the lamp will increase (UV irradiation x time) the performance of this UV-C lamp.

The estimated travel time is about 200 sec. The LEDs wavelength will be between 265 and 285 nm. Other characteristics are Mercury free, remote start/stop, low power consumption, UV lamp Safety Interlock.

Table 4-8. UV-C lamp technical characteristics

UV-Transmittance	> 90% recommended				
Headloss at Max Flow [psi (bar)]	1.5 (0.1)	2 (0.1)	2.2 (0.2)	1.5 (0.1)	1.3 (0.1)
Inlet/Outlet Connection	1/4"	1/4"	3/8"	1/2"	1/2"
Weight [kg (lbs)]	1.2 (2.7)	1.6 (3.5)	1.6 (3.5)	2.1 (4.6)	3.3 (7.3)
Max Pressure [psi (bar)]	100 (6.9)				
Water Temperature [°C (°F)]	0-50 (32-122)				
Environmental Protection	IP65				
Lamp Life [hours]	up to 10,000				
Input Power [V DC]	12				
Power Consumption [W]	8	12	15	20	24

Water condensed pump

Free Water Pump is a removing system for the unloading of condensation water; it is made up of a pump block and a level measurement block, with switch. Fig. 4-14 shows the characteristics of this pump:

Figure 4-14 Condensed water pump and level switch.

Technical Characteristics

- Payload 12,6 l/hour : with the requirement of 2 l/h max, duty cycle of 10 min/hour.
- Maximum aspiration: 2 vertical meters between the measure block and pump
- Maximum transmission: 10 vertical meters between pump and water output
- Voltage 230 VAC / 50 Hz
- Pump dimensions L30 X D80 X H57 mm
- Measure block dimensions L31 X D91 X H49 mm

Note that during the MTF assembly integration and test phase the condensate pump was replaced with an Aspen Pumps, mini tank condensate removal pump – part number: 1056/2 (Figure 4-14). This pump was preferred due to issues of growth through the transparent housing and the high on/off cycle rate of the previous pump due to its smaller internal reservoir size.

Figure 4-15 Updated condensate water pump with internal level switch from Aspen Pumps.

A condensate flowmeter was also selected and installed following the pump within the condensate collection line. The selected flowmeter is from B.I.O-TEK e.K. and is from the FCH-midi-POM series. The low flow flowmeter can measure flows between 0.3 and 10 L/min and provides ca. 930 impulses per litre.

Figure 4-16 Employed flowmeter from B.I.O-Teck to measure total collected condensate water.

4.2.5 Heaters

The amount of needed heating is calculated considering these boundary conditions:

- Air temperature exiting from the dehumidifier (see Table 2-5) : 15,7 °C with 95,5% of RH
- Air temperature at the FEG inlet: 20,5 °C with related RH

Start Point	Process	Current Point
Dehumidifer outle	Connect State Points	DB 20,5 W 10,68000
Air Flow 390 DB 15,700 WB 15,249 RH 95,50 W 10,68 v 0,832 h 42,720 DP 14,978 d 1,2148 vp 12,7736 AW 12,835	<input type="checkbox"/> Total Energy 2.305 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Energy 2.304 <input type="checkbox"/> Latent Energy 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Moisture Difference 0,0 <input type="checkbox"/> Sensible Heat Ratio 0,999 <input type="checkbox"/> Enthalpy/Humidity Ratio 4.164,051	Air Flow 390 DB 20,500 WB 16,967 RH 70,62 W 10,68 v 0,846 h 47,642 DP 14,983 d 1,1949 vp 12,7782 AW 12,627

LEGENDA

Air Flow L/sec
 DB Dry Bulb temperature °C
 WB Wet Bulb temperature °C
 RH Relative Humidity %
 W Water content g/kg
 v Specific Volume m³/kg
 h Enthalpy kJ/kg
 DP Dew Point temperature °C
 d density kg/m³
 vp Vapour pressure mmHG
 AW Absolute Humidity g/m³

PROCESS PARAMETERS

Total Cooling W
 Total Energy W
 Sensible Energy W
 Latent Energy W
 Dehumidification kg/h
 Sensible Heat Ratio
 Enthalpy/Humidity Ratio kJ/kg/g/kg

Table 4-9: Heating calculation.

The heating capacity calculated is 2.304 W: in order to have a safety margin, it has been selected heaters for a 3.000 W of total capacity (3 x 1 kW each).

Figure 4-17: Heater for duct installation.

4.2.6 Filtration

This subassembly is composed of:

- UV-C Lamp, air
- Mechanical Filtration, HEPA filter, with a prefilter,
- Chemical Filtration, VOC filter.

UV-C Lamp

Aim of the application of an UV-C lamp 260 nm of wavelength is both the decontamination of the surface of the dehumidifier and the Airborne Inactivation, to eliminate the microbial load. In these micro-areas of shadow, between the metal wings of the thermal batteries, colonies of fungi, algae, and bacteria are established, due to the high levels of humidity. The device works by direct irradiation of UV-C rays. When the tube is turned on, it reduces the microbial load in the air and on the surfaces enlightened by the UV lamp.

The selected lamp is UV-DUCT-FL 2/60HP-LA and is shown in following figures. This module consists of a flanged structure from which two U shaped UV lamps come out, protected by a stainless steel grid.

A typical configuration places the UV-C lights upstream from the cooling coil to deal with the spore size micro-organisms and upstream of a high efficiency HEPA (High Efficiency Particulate Arrestance) filter to eliminate airborne bacteria and viral contaminants.

Figure 4-18: UV-C Lamp.

Table 4-10 UV-C Technical Characteristics.

UV-DUCT-FL	2/35HP	2/60HP	2/95HP
AVERAGE LAMP LIFETIME (hours)	9000	9000	9000
CONSUMPTION (W)	70	120	190
DIMENSIONS lxsxh	410x130x278	410x130x477	410x130x603
"A" LENGTH (mm.)	183	382	508
WEIGHT (Kg.)	2	2	2,5
AIR FLOW (m ³)*	1.000÷2.400	1.300÷3.400	2.200÷5.600

Figure 4-19: UV-C Lamp 3D model.

Figure 4-20: UV-C Lamp installation in Duct.

For the disinfection efficiency compared with this flow rate, it has been selected a lamp of 120 W, as shown in Table 4-10, manufactured by Light Progress (www.lightprogress.it).

Absolute filter and prefilter

The prefilter is class F7 per EN ISO772, and protects the HEPA filter from the coarse powder. This filter is made by a panel of polyester fiber, 40 mm of thickness, installed directly of the upper face of the absolute filter

The Absolute filter is HEPA 14 classified, with efficiency EN1822-2009 of 99,995%

These filters have mini pleated microfiber glass filtering pack, top quality manufacture, high dust holding capacity and great mechanical resistance.

At the nominal flow rate of 1400 m3/h the pressure drop of the filter new will be 300 Pa. This filter has a pressure drop control: when the pressure reaches the value double than the new one, the filter has to be changed. For this purpose in the pressure drop calculation was considered the final pressure drop of 600 Pa. Fig. 4-19 shows the installation of the Absolute Filter in the duct system.

Figure 4-21: Absolute HEPA Filter Installation.

VOC Filter

Main Driving parameters for the VOC filter are:

- Quantity of VOC (Ethylene ref.) to be absorb
- Speed of the air through the filtration bed, to have the best efficiency

The ethylene production is:

pp Ethylene_{max} 15 ppb continuous (15 mg/m³)

In order to guarantee a filter lifetime at least of 6 months with a safety margin of 20%, the quantity of ethylene to be stored will be 108 g (216 g for 1 year).

One of the most performant filter media for Ethylene (C₂H₄) is spheres of alumina impregnated with potassium permanganate(KMnO₄), capable of removing H₂S, SO₂, NO_x, Ethylene, kerosene and Hydrocarbons through oxidation process.

Figure 4-22: VOC filter container.

To provide an adsorption system for the removal of other VOCs beside Ethylene, this media may be use blended with activated carbon that combines broad spectrum and highly specific characteristics. The selected blend ratio is 50/50 by volume.

In order to have a standard dimensions for the installation in the duct, the VOC filter will be realized with a container as shown in Figure 4-22 (ref. Camfil).

The Ethylene removal capacity for this type of filter media is of 1,5-2% by weight (0,012-0,016 g/cc). Maximum quantity of Ethylene adsorbed will be:

$$28.000 \text{ cc} \times 0,012 \text{ g/cc} = 336 \text{ g}$$

Comparing this value with the foreseen ethylene production, the filter will have a lifetime of:
 $336 / (216) = 1,5$ year.

Table 4-11: Filter media characteristics.

Contaminant Gas	g/cc	Weight % *
Hydrogen sulfide (H ₂ S)	0.1120	14.00
Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂)	0.0560	7.00
Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	0.1684	20.96
Nitric oxide (NO)	0.0394	4.93
Formaldehyde (HCHO)	0.0200	2.50

Temperature	-4°F to 125°F (-20°C to 51°C)
Humidity	10 - 95% RH
Air Speed	60 - 500 fpm (0.30 - 2.54 m/s)

Filter installation

Fig. 4-21 shows the installation of VOC filter in the duct system.

Figure 4-23- VOC Filter installation.

Figure 4-24: Filter Duct Casing.

4.2.7 Air distribution

Driving parameters:

- Flow rate 1400 m³/h
- Air speed inside ducts: 3 m/sec ref.
- Air speed on crop: 0,2 m/sec with a minimum launch of 600-700 mm, depth of the shelf

Duct dimensioning:

- Main duct: 700 x 170 mm, air speed 3,24 m/sec.
- First subdivision: 2 duct, right and left, 700 m³/h each, 350 x 170 mm air speed 3,24 m/sec, constant.
- Second subdivision: 4 horizontal lines for each side, 175 m³/h each.
- Those ducts are divided in 4 parts, with constant height of 200 mm and variable depth decreasing from 80 mm the first part, 65mm the second, 50 mm the third and 24mm the last.
- Each of these ducts will have side openings to spread the air at the speed close to 0,4 m/sec, so each opening will have a free area of 0,24 m² (175 m³/h/0,24 m² = 0,2 m/sec).
- Main Return air duct is: 700x170 mm, air speed 3,24 m/sec.
- To improve the distribution of the air and the temperature in FEG, 8 tangential fans at the top of each shelf will be installed, in order to aspire the air from the top of the FEG and to give it a direction to the bottom.

The development of the duct system is depicted in figures below. Fig.4-24 shows the pressure duct starting from the bottom of the AMS unit and the two secondary ducts at the inlet in FEG, bottom part. In blue is depicted the suction duct, from the FEG to the upper part of the AMS unit:

Figure 4-25: Ducts in SS.

Fig. 4-25 shows the duct in SS with the constant flow valves, the flexible tubes and the 8 horizontal ducts, with the 64 louvers.

Figure 4-26: Ducts development in FEG.

A first trade-off has been performed to choose the type of the horizontal duct, between textile duct, or rigid. It was selected the rigid type to allow the installation of louvers, settable and closable.

A second trade off was performed between the shape: oval or rectangular. Towards the pressure drop the oval size would be better but the rectangular one has been selected because of the possibility to better customize shape and dimensions.

Finally, the last trade off was about the shape: the final choice is a variable shape, in four part: the first part has a section of 200x80 mm , the second 200 x 65 mm, the third 200x 50 mm and the last 200 x 24 mm. With this geometry it has been obtained the better uniformity about the air velocity and the uniformity of the air distribution.

Figure 4-27: Horizontal duct with variable section.

Fig. 4-27 shows the details of louvers, of a series of holes on the top and on the bottom part of the ducts to move air along the FEG walls and of one of the reductions that allow the installation of these ducts where there is the change of width.

Figure 4-28: Horizontal duct longitudinal section.

Figure 4-29: Detail of Louver.

The correct selection of louvers can guarantee uniform distribution of the air between the ducts, but if one or more louvers will be closed, this distribution can change. To avoid this, the installation of constant flow valves in each duct was foreseen.

Figure 4-30: Constant Flow valve installation.

This type of valve can be preset at a defined value and they will maintain automatically this value also within a pressure change in the air, due for example at the partial closure of some louvers.

The RV series volume flow controller work with a free-moving control plate, It has an automatic actuator that, without the use of auxiliary power, is capable of maintaining the air flow constant within a predefined field of differential pressures. The controller operates reliably from a minimum pressure difference, which depends on the air velocity, to a maximum pressure difference of 1000 Pa. The flow rate variation is within a tolerance of $\pm 10\%$.

The controller operates within a temperature range from -30°C to 100°C .

Dati dimensionali/Dimensions RV							
Grandezza/Size	Qmin [m ³ /h]	Qmax [m ³ /h]	A [mm]	B [mm]	C [mm]	Z [mm]	ΦD [mm]
80	40	125	200	120	40	70	79

Figure 4-31. Constant Flow RV80.

The flow rate for each duct is 175 m³/h and the size of the duct 200 x 80 mm.

To fit the dimensions of each duct of 200 x 80 with the dimensions of the valves, there is the need to install two valves, 80 mm of diameter, set at 175/2 ≈ 90 m³/h, for each duct.

The air volume controllers are supplied ready-calibrated in line at 85 m³/h each. By using a 2 mm Allen key, the air flow can easily be regulated within the range requested.

Figure 4-32: Setting of the valve.

Flexible Tubes

Figure 4-31 shows the circular flexible duct selected, after a trade off towards the rigid tube has been performed (more or less same pressure loss and easier installation for flexible type).

Code - A8G17....AS
Base Material - PU
Operating Temperature - -40 ÷ +100 °C
Pressure - 0,01 ÷ 0,65 bar
Vacuum - 0,10 ÷ 3,06 mtH2O
Diameter Range - 25 ÷ 600 mm
Key Feature - Transparent, Anti-static, Spiral hose

Figure 4-33: Flexible tube 80 mm diameter.

Figure 4-34. Flexible tubes construction.

Materials of this type of tube are high quality antistatic polyurethane polyester sheet and a coppered armonic steel wire helix embodied into the sheet layers utilization of a polyurethane profile gives to the hose an excellent tear resistance (seven times more than PVC) excellent flexibility, even at low temperatures - axial compression 6:1 anti-static: $R_o < 10$ according to DIN 53846. Suitable to be used in areas with the risk of degradation or where an electrostatic charge should modify the conveyed elements, excellent resistance to oils, fats and several solvents, good resistance to chemical agents good resistance also to UV, even if a typical polyurethane characteristic is photosensitivity and colour alterations may occur, that turns to yellowing, but not affecting its qualities.

FEG air circulation Tangential fans

As said, in order to keep a homogeneous circulation of air in each points of the FEG, it has been designed and calculated the installation of fans, tangential type, on the top of the shelves, one for each. The following pictures show the selected model with the performance curve and dimensions.

The working point chosen is 300 m³/h, with a consumption of 72 W (total 72 x 8 = 576W).

Table 3-12: Tangential Fan Performance.

Type	QLN65/3030-3045	
Phase	1~	
Nominal voltage	VAC	230
Frequency	Hz	50
Speed	min ⁻¹	1225
Power input	W	72
Current draw	A	0.56
Min. ambient temperature	°C	0
Max. ambient temperature	°C	60
Air flow	m ³ /h	410
Pressure increase	Pa	62

Figure 4-35: Tangential fan dimensions.

The Fig. 4-34 shows the position of the tangential fans in FEG, one for each shelf.

Figure 4-36: Tangential fans installation.

4.2.8 CO₂ System

Requirements:

- Maintain a Level of CO₂ = 650 ppm, ppCO₂, max = 1500 (24 hours) (germination phase & cucumber is limiting)
- Air Leakage from the FEG structure: 500% total FEG volumes per day (note that this considers leakage from the FEG – not the MTF overall).
- CO₂ Requirements – 370 g/day (actual calculated)

The CO₂ system will be composed of CO₂ storage , an injection and distribution system, sensors and controller.

The needing CO₂ during the operations will be supplied by two cylinders, connected by a semi-automatic gas panel, Linde A 208, see Fig. 3-35. The cylinders are connected two at the time, but only one is working.

Figure 4-37- CO₂ Plant, external part.

The CO₂ distribution is shown in Fig.4-36. The Gas panel A 208 is a semi-automatic gas panel designed for uninterrupted gas supply. Switch-over between the two connected cylinders or bundles occurs when the pressure of one side (the primary side) falls below a pre-set pressure level. This is achieved by two integrated regulators (factory-set to slightly different delivery pressure levels) which are connected at their outlet ports. The cylinders are installed outside, so the pressure values when the temperature becomes cold are very low and can be difficult to read the pressure difference. In that case it has to do a visual control of the gauges and a manual activation of the commutation valves. After the Gas Panel A208 there is the panel W20 regulator: by this panel it is possible to set the value of the CO₂ pressure.

Figure 4-38. CO₂ schematic.

The tube comes through the container wall until a solenoid valve.

Figure 4-39. Regulator Panel W20.

Figure 4-40. A 208 semi-automatic gas panel.

This valve depicted in Fig. 4-39 is a three way direct acting solenoid valve with spring return. The valve is controlled by ARGUS system between the signal of Low CO₂ level received by the sensors located closer the Crop in FEG. The injection with gas CO₂ has a central header placed in the air duct after the thermal control, dehumidifier and heaters, see Fig. 4-40.

The potential for low CO₂ levels inside a dense crop canopy makes it beneficial to supplement within the canopy. Air movement around the plants will also improve the CO₂ uptake because the boundary layer around the individual leaf is lessened bringing the CO₂ molecules closer to the leaf.

Figure 4-41. CO2 Injection Solenoid Valve.

Figure 4-42. CO₂ Injection point.

It is important to have an adequate distribution system. The distribution of CO₂ depends mainly on air movement within the FEG as CO₂ does not travel very far through diffusion. Air circulation provides uniform distribution by moving large volumes of air within the FEG. The potential for low CO₂ levels inside a dense crop canopy makes it beneficial to supplement within the canopy. Air movement around the plants will also improve the CO₂ uptake because the boundary layer around the individual leaf is lessened bringing the CO₂ molecules closer to the leaf.

The storage will be done by 145 kg of CO₂ useable for 1 year of operations, kept in cylinders.

4.2.9 Control System- Sensors

The sensors installed on the AMS system are:

- Temperature and RH
- CO₂
- O₂
- Air flow rate
- Pressure differential

Temperature and RH:

EE071 is optimized for use in demanding OEM applications. Beside humidity and temperature measured values calculated variables like dew point and mixing ratio are also available at the output. The standard modbus RTU protocol is implemented on the RS485 interface.

Figure 4-43: Temperature and RH sensor.

Table 4-13 summarizes the technical characteristics of this sensor:

Table 4-13. Characteristics of Temperature and RH sensor.

General

Supply voltage	4 - 18V DC
Current consumption	typ. 0.4mA at a measuring rate of 1 sec.
Current pulse during power-up (with serial resistance 100 Ohm)	at UB 7V: I _{max} 60mA; current draw drops below 10mA within 350µs at UB 12V: I _{max} 110mA; current draw drops below 10mA within 400µs
Warmup Time	< 300ms
Output load	no bus termination no pullup or pulldown resistor } within probe
Interface	RS485 / Modbus in slavemode
Housing	polycarbonate or stainless steel / IP65
Electromagnetic compatibility ¹⁾	EN613216-1 EN61326-2-3 FCC Part 15 Class B ICES-003 Issue 5 ClassB
Working and storage temperature	-40...80°C (-40...176°F)
Max. cable length	100m (328.1ft)

1) Not protected against surge

Dimensions in mm (inch)

polycarbonate housing - EE071-HTPx

metal housing - EE071-HTMx

CO₂ Sensor

CO₂ level are measured within the FEG using Argus ventilated boxes the provide temperature, relative humidity, CO₂ and rough light values. CO₂ can be measured to a maximum of 2000 ppm with these sensors. Additionally, a CO₂ safety system is also incorporated into the MTF.

O₂ Sensor

O₂Tracer 4 – 20 mA Loop Powered two wire Oxygen Transmitter
 Ref: Roscid Technologies

Ordering Number	Range
O2T-1	0-10%
O2T-2	0-25%
O2T-3	0-100%

Figure 4-44: O₂ Sensor.

Housing: IP65
 Size: 3.15 x 3 x 2.17 (B x H x T (mm))
 Accuracy: +/- 2% FSD T= const.
 +/- 5% FSD 0>T>50°C
 Signal output: 4 -20 mA / DC
 Voltage: 10 – 35 VDC

Air Flow Sensor

Temperature	Process: -40 to 212°F
Limits	Ambient: 32 to 140°F
Pressure Limit	100 psi (6.89 bar) maximum
Humidity Limit	Non-condensing
Power Requirements	12-35 VDC, 10-16 VAC. 1.5 A rating required on supply due to initial power surge drawn by transmitter
Output Signal	4-20 mA, isolated 24V source, 3 or 4-wire connection

Ref: Dwyer Instruments mod. 641-12

Figure 4-45: Air flow sensor.

Differential pressure sensor

This type of instrument is used to monitor the mechanical filters, like the absolute filter and the pre-filter. When the differential pressure reaches the set value, it means that the filter is cloggy and it has to be removed.

Figure 4-46: Series 605 Magnehelic Differential Pressure indicating transmitter.

Series 605 Magnehelic® Differential Pressure Indicating Transmitter, Range .25-0-.25" w.c., Max. Pressure 25 psi (1.7 bar), $\pm 2\%$ Electrical Accuracy, $\pm 3\%$ Mechanical Accuracy. The Series 605 Magnehelic® Indicating Transmitter provides for both visual monitoring and electronic control of very low differential pressure. The Series 605 is ideal for control applications in building HVAC systems where local indication is desired during routine maintenance checks or necessary when trouble shooting the system. The easily read dial gage is complimented by the two-wire, 4-20 mA control signal utilizing the time-proven Dwyer® Magnehelic® gage mechanical design and Series 600 transmitter technology. The two-wire design with terminal strip on the rear simplifies connection in any 4-20mA control loop powered by a 10-35 VDC supply.

Figure 4-47. Differential Pressure Gauge installed.

4.3 Options and trades

In the follow the relevant trade-offs conducted through the design process are summarized and briefly described.

- 1- Tubes connecting the main pressure ducts with the horizontal ducts

Decision between rigid type or flexible type

The flexible type wins, for easier installation with the same pressure drop

- 2- Horizontal ducts, made with fabric or rigid: the rigid solution has been chosen, suitable for the installation of louvers, settable and closable.

- 3- Trade-off between the shape of the ducts, oval or rectangular.

The selected shape was the rectangular, which has a little bit more pressure drop but in this case it is available to be made with customized dimensions (duct with variable width).

- 4- Position of constant flow valves, A or B: B wins, because of easier installation and possibility to respect the installation recommendations of the supplier.

5- Shape of the horizontal ducts

Before obtaining the final design of the shape of those ducts, a number of trade-offs between different geometries were performed. The following is a summary of this activity.

Duct with variable width: simulation results

VOLUMETRIC FLOW (m³/h)	OUT1	OUT2	OUT3	OUT4	OUT5	OUT6	OUT7	OUT 8	Holes UP	Holes DOWN
CONSTANT WIDTH	-8.8	8.7	7.1	6.5	6.5	11.3	28.3	55.2	29.8	30.4
VARIABLE WIDTH	18.0	18.9	15.6	15.6	13.6	19.2	20.1	14.0	19.4	20.5

- Considering a geometry with variable width, the flow split has a good balance: a final regulation of the flow can be done directly on each single louver.
- The average velocity on louvers is 0.37[m/s] (geometry with variable width).
- The average velocity on up/down holes is 0.65[m/s] (geometry with variable width).

6- Suction duct and air distribution

In this case four different solutions were examined: three types of return duct geometries and one without duct but adding fans on the top of FEG. On the base of 3D simulations, this last solution has been selected.

Return duct sol. 1

Return duct solution 2

- The two suction ducts could be made longer and suck air near bottom part of the FEG

Return duct solution 3

Solution 4, proposal of additional fans on the top of FEG

Final solution, 8 fans, type tangential:

4.4 Subsystem key values

Table 4-14 provides an overview of the key values for the AMS FEG system.

Table 4-14: Key values of the AMS FEG subsystem.

	Mass	Peak power	Power day - nominal mode	Power night - nominal mode	Cost
AMS unit	[kg]	[W]	[W]	[W]	[€]
- Air circulation	18	1.500	1.382	900 ¹	1.900
-Dehumidification	24	66	66	36 ²	2.008
-Heater	16	3.000	2.150	2.340	900
-Filtration	80	120	120	120	5.470
-Rack-devices	150	NA	NA	NA	4.568
Air distribution	320	576	576	576	21.280
CO₂ system	54	NA	NA	NA	4.600
Sensors system	20	20	20	20	4.936
TOTAL	702 kg	5.552 W	4.584 W	4.127 W	48.662

Note

1. Flow rate reduced at 800 m³/h (tbc by horticulture)
2. 40 W pump and 16 W UV lamp- when the transpiration decrease, pump duty cycle at 50%

5 AMS FEG Operations

In this section, will be described the Air Management System will be operated.

5.1 Nominal operations

Automatic and operator actions relevant to normal operations.

.....

AMS operations

As described in the above sections, the Air Management System is composed by an AMS unit, an Air distribution, a humidification, a CO₂ system and an ambient parameters monitoring.

Most part of the signals and the commands necessary to monitor and actuate the systems are sent to and received from a remote control panel (Power supply system) and managed by Argus, an automated control system of greenhouse environments.

The functions that can be operated in local are related to the Air distribution, in detail constant flow valves- louvers and tangential fans, and to the AMS unit, mainly control and substitution of filters.

In the AMS unit, the fans (2) are activated always, because it has to keep the air in movement continuously. These fans have an alarm relay to signal the failure on remote panel and a control input 0-10 VDC/PWM. Acting on that is possible to change the speed of fan and of consequence the performances and the power consumption. During the functional tests, it has been verified that the performance of the fans can be reached at the 70% of the maximum power supply. The control of the fans is made also by a flow meter, installed on a suction duct, before the fans. Those flow meter has an output signals 4-20 mA suitable for alarms (i.e. the fan is shut off) and for a limitation of the fan speed.

In the dehumidification function the temperature of the heat exchanger is kept constant (by the Thermal Control). The air temperature is checked by two temperature transmitters, one at the outlet of the FEG and one at the inlet: those sensors activate the heater (from 0 to 3 kW) to obtain the set value. The function water condensed recovery is automatic: a level sensor in the water condensed line before the pump, activates this pump, with an on-off logic type.

Figure 5-1. Water condensed schematic.

The function done by the O₂ sensor, installed at the outlet of the FEG, is to send a measure of the O₂ level to the control panel, just to record the O₂ production.

Filter replacement

Manual operations are required for the filtration function. Three filters are installed in the AMS unit: a prefilter, an absolute HEPA filter and a VOC (Ethylene) filter. Prefilter and absolute filter are controllable by a pressure differential gauge because they change the pressure drop when clogged. The gauge display has to be checked visually: when the pressure level reaches the value of 600 Pa the filters are to substitute. This operation is easy, by a frontal panel with 4 latches, manually screwed without tools. For the VOC filter, chemical type, the pressure drop doesn't change: the only possible control is the colour change of the filter media, visible through a sight seen directly put on the filter case, so in local. The procedure to change this filter is the same of the previous filters.

Anyway the filters are designed for a duration of prefilter 3 months, absolute filter 6 months and VOC scrubber > 1 year: after those periods it is suggested to change the filters, also less a clogged filter alarm or a change colour of filter media.

CO₂

The CO₂ sensors are installed at the outlet of the FEG and one at the inlet, after a CO₂ injection point (re. Functional schematic). In this case, those sensors will send a signal of the CO₂ level to remote panel (Argus). From this panel will start a command, in case of level lower than the set value, to open the solenoid valve which intercepts the gas line before the injection point. The CO₂ quantity injected will be regulated on the basis of number of openings of the solenoid valve, keeping a constant opening time. It has to define the opening time of the valve, on the base of physical test.

Fig.4-35 shows the cylinder change when empty, with manual valves.

Setting of louvers and constant flow valves

The air distribution system within the FEG has some manual operations to change the default setting. First of all, the louvers installed on the horizontal ducts are closable, partially or totally, in order to change the air quantity for different zones of the shelves.

It is possible to change the setting of the constant flow valves. Now those are all set at a design point of 85 m³/h. In case of change of the design conditions it will be possible to move the set of each valve.

See Fig. 4-30.

Another manually operation will be the control of the speed of the tangential fans (8) installed on the top of FEG to improve the air circulation : for each fan is available near the fan, in local, a speed controller manually operated, in order to fine adjust, if necessary, the air circulation.

The last functional block of the AMS is the humidification.

In nominal operations it is not foreseen that a humidifier is needed in the FEG. If testing or initial operations indicates otherwise, the operator will place a standalone humidifier in the FEG. The operator will then refill the humidifier as needed.

Preventive maintenance

As described before, most part of the operations are automatic.

A preventive maintenance can be based on:

- a check list that all the parameters controlled by sensors are in the required range
- a control of the water level in the condensed water tank (an obstruction can be cause flooding)
- control of the mechanical filters status: pressure value on pressure differential display
- control of the VOCl filters status: media colour. Virgin color is purple, sorbent may change color during application indicating chemical reaction of removal of targeted contaminants.
- control of humidifier connections with the internal water piping (flood risk)

- control of the CO₂ level in the storage cylinders
- check of the measures detected by the sensors with an independent one
- check the air distribution measuring the air velocity at the outlet of the louvers with the proper air velocity and temperature flow meter supplied with the system (see Fig.5-2 below).

Figure 5-2. Hot wire anemometer.

To state a corrective maintenance it has to define before a troubleshooting, comparing all the information with the function logic of Argus and the alarms on the control panel.

5.2 Off-Nominal operations

Operator actions relevant to off-nominal operations (including troubleshooting steps).

1	Main Fans	Air flow rate in the air circulation system below the design requirements	Alarm from air flow meter	Check the power absorbed	Replace the fan
2	Tangential fans	It does not air	Visually check	Verify the regulator	Replace the regulator or the fan
3	CO ₂ distribution	CO ₂ level is not kept	Argus sensor gives alarm	Check the pressure gauges on panel A208	Replace the cylinder empty

5.3 Maintenance and spares

The spares supplied with the AMS are:

N°.	Description	Qty	Normal Frequency	Off-nominal
1	UV-Lamp	1	NA	In case of failure
2	Carbon filter Cartridges	1	After 1 year of operation	Before if the colour of alumina spheres change from purple
3	HEPA Filter	3	After 6 months	Before if the differential pressure reaches 600 Pa
4	Prefilter	4	After 6 months	Change with HEPA filter
5	Main Fan	1	NA	In case of failure
6	Tangential Fan	2	NA	In case of failure

5.4 Preparation for shipment

There are no particular recommendations to prepare the subsystem for shipment (e.g. to Antarctica).

The only parts that can travel safer disassembled are the two UV-C lamps. No other special shipping requirements are foreseen.

6 Parts list

The parts lists presented below only incorporate items which may need to be replaced. As such, filter casings and ducting is not included.

Table 7-1: Parts list for the AMS Service Section system.

Element/Part	Qty	Spares	Manufacturer	Part Number
COLD PORCH				
Flow control valve	1	0	Blauberg Ventilatoren	VKA 160
Valve actuator	1	1	Siemens	GQD321-1A
Heater	2	0	Helios GmbH	01090009
Pre-filter (F7 class)	1	3	Luftfilterbau GmbH	HS-BETA Pak 85
HEPA filter (H13 class)	1	3	Luftfilterbau GmbH	HS-MIKRO SF
Fan	1	1	Blauberg Ventilatoren	ISO 160-2E
Humidifier	1	1	BOGA GmbH	Airwin UB-1D

Table 7-2: Parts list for the AMS FEG system.

Element/Part	Qty	Spares	Manufacturer	Part Number
SERVICE SECTION				
UV-lamp	2	1	Light Progress	UV-DUCT-FL 2/60HP-LA
Carbon filter cartridges	1	1	Camfil	30 CAMCARB VG300 121212 BLENDCEX003/CAMPURE 8
Pre-filter	1	3	CLR	595x287x48
HEPA filter	1	2	Camfil	VEXL-14-305-610-292-PR-5
Main fan	2	1	Ebm-papst	K3G 250-AT39-74
Condensate water pump	1	1	Aspen Pumps	Mini Tank 1056/2
Condensate flow sensor	1	1	B.I.O-TECH	FCH-midi-POM, 503593
Condensate water UV-lamp	1	1	Aquisense	PearlAqua
Condensate water filter	1	4	Leroy Merlin	Active carbon cartridge 5"
Flow meter	1	-	Dwyer	DS641
O2 tracer	1	-	Roscid technologies	60716 RT
CO2 injection valve	1	-	NADI	CO2-18 tco
Constant Flow Valve	16	2	Roccheggiani	RV 80
FEG				
Tangential Fan	8	2	Ebm-papst	QLN65.3030-304

7 Thermal System Top-level design overview

The thermal control system has to dissipate the larger part of the heat produced inside the entire MTF. Specifically, the thermal system will dissipate the heat from three sources: the ISPR, the AMS and the LED panels in the FEG.

Cooling lines filled with a water-Tyfocon mixture will be used to transport heat from the sources to liquid-liquid heat exchangers. A water-Tyfoxit mixture will then transport the heat from the heat exchangers to a roof-mounted heat rejection unit, known as a free cooler. The free cooler can be seen mounted on top of the MTF in Figure 1-1.

The characteristics of Tyfocon and Tyfoxit can be found in the Appendix.

Figure 1-1: Free cooler mounted on the roof of the MTF.

The position of the three main heat sources is shown in Figure 1-2 and Figure 1-3. The AMS and ISPR thermal loops are both situated within the Service Section. The thermal loop for the LEDs runs from the Service Section to the FEG, to the LEDs, and then back to the Service Section to the plate heat exchanger.

Figure 1-2: Service Section cut view – South side.

Figure 1-3: FEG cut view – North side.

The components of the thermal control system and their positioning are shown in greater detail in Figure 1-4 and Figure 1-5.

Figure 1-4: Position of plate heat exchangers, accumulator tanks and interfaces.

Figure 1-5: Thermal control system, prior to integration in the MTF.

8 Thermal System Detailed design

8.1 Block diagram(s)

The block diagram of the thermal control system is shown in the Appendix of this document.

The thermal system can be roughly divided into three sections: The thermal loop for the AMS dehumidifier, the thermal loop for the ISPR and LEDs, and the 'external' loop which connects those two thermal loops with the external heat rejection unit.

The AMS thermal loop and the ISPR and LED thermal loop have a similar architecture. A pump with an expansion vessel forces a coolant liquid through the system (AMS dehumidifier, LED cold plate, or ISPR) and then towards a heat exchanger. A number of sensors are incorporated to determine temperature, flow rate and pressure loss. Three-way valves allow automatic adjustment of the amount of heat which is transferred away from the heat sources, in order to maintain coolant temperatures within a specified range. The architecture in the FEG utilizes flow control valves to balance the flow rate over the different racks and the levels within each rack.

The 'external' thermal loop handles the opposite side of the two heat exchangers, supplying a cold coolant liquid and transporting the 'hot' coolant liquid to the externally located heat rejection unit. Again the set-up is fairly straightforward, with a pump and expansion vessel ensuring the desired flow rate is met and sensors providing the required data for control of the actuators.

8.2 System sizing/analyses

To size the thermal system, first the thermal loads which need to be dissipated have to be known. An overview of these values for the three heat sources is given in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: Thermal loads imposed on the thermal system.

Heat Source	Thermal load
AMS	6600 W
ISPR	1300 W
LED	4100 W

For compatibility with the thermal system in place on the ISS, the supply temperature of the cooling water to the ISPR will be between 16 and 20°C. A similar supply temperature will be used for the LED cooling fluid.

On account of the significantly higher thermal load of the AMS, as well as the lower air temperatures which need to be reached through cooling of the FEG air, the cooling fluid supply temperature for this cooling loop will be lower, between 6 and 10°C.

As with the coolant supply temperature, the maximum flow rate for the ISPR cooling loop is also fixed, at 190 kg/hr. This enables the calculation of the return temperature of the coolant fluid, using Equation 1.

Equation 4

$$\Delta T = \frac{\dot{q}}{c\dot{m}} = \frac{1300\text{W} * 3600 \frac{\text{s}}{\text{h}}}{4185.5 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg} * \text{K}} * 190 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{h}}} \approx 5.9^\circ\text{C}$$

For the AMS and LED cooling loops, the maximum flow rate and the return temperature are design parameters which can be adjusted to find an optimal solution.

For the initial sizing described in this document, the assumption is made that the return temperature of the ISPR and LED cooling lines is the same. For the AMS cooling line it is assumed that the supply

temperature is 8°C and the flow rate is 1100 kg/hr, based on an initial design of the AMS dehumidifier. Adapting Equation 1 then allows us to determine the corresponding return temperature.

An overview of the supply temperature, return temperature and flow rate for the three cooling loops is presented in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2: Supply and return temperature, as well as flow rate, for the thermal cooling loops.

	Supply temperature	Return temperature	Flow rate
AMS	8°C	15.2°C	1100 kg/hr
ISPR	20°C	25.9°C	190 kg/hr
LED	20°C	25.9°C	~440 kg/hr

The flow rates, along with the estimated pressure losses through the cooling loops enable the selection of the pumps which will force the coolant through the cooling loops. The pressure losses in the ISPR cold plate, the LED cold plates and the AMS dehumidifier are listed below in Table 2-3.

Table 2-3: Thermal load source pressure losses.

	Pressure loss
AMS	72.9 kPa
ISPR	21.3 kPa
LED	6 kPa

Note that the pressure loss value listed for the LEDs is the pressure loss per two panels. This value does not yet include the losses due to the fittings to which the piping will be connected. Additional pressure losses have been determined based on pipe length and diameter, height differences, valves, and other components of the piping architecture. An overview of the various pressure losses can be found in the Appendix.

The water cooling loops transfer heat away from the three main heat sources, towards two plate heat exchangers, one for the AMS system and one for the ISPR and LEDs. At the heat exchangers, the heat from the water-Tyfocor cooling loops is transferred to the water-Tyfoxit mixture and subsequently pumped to the external heat rejection unit.

The plate heat exchangers can be sized based on the amount of heat which needs to be transferred. Then, assuming a certain heat transfer coefficient for the plate heat exchanger and for a given temperature difference between the inlet temperatures of both cooling fluids, Equation 2 can be used to calculate the required heat exchanger area.

A typical heat transfer coefficient for a plate heat exchanger is in the range of 1000-4000 W/m²K. For the example calculation the inlet temperature of the water-Tyfocor mixture is assumed to be 0°C.

Equation 5

$$A = \frac{\dot{q}}{U\Delta T_{1-2}} = \frac{6600}{1000 * 15.2} = 0.434m^2$$

As shown in Equation 2, the heat exchanger area for the AMS heat exchanger, under these assumptions, would be 0.434 m². For the ISPR and LED heat exchanger an area of 0.166 m² can be calculated.

Using multiple smaller plates would allow for a very compact heat exchanger. However, the size, heat transfer coefficient and pressure losses associated with the plate heat exchanger are all design parameters which need to be considered to find an optimal solution.

The final step in the heat dissipation system is the transfer of heat from the water-Tyfoxit mixture, via the heat rejection unit, to the external environment. The free cooler selection was based on the expected external temperatures in the Antarctic and the maximum thermal load which needs to be

rejected. The characteristics of the final selected components can be found in the Appendix to this document.

8.3 Options and trades

The initial design of the thermal system during the Concurrent Engineering study in September 2015, as described in the Preliminary Design Report, envisioned three separate cooling systems; one for each of the three systems which have to be cooled (see block diagram in Figure 2-1). Each cooling system would have the same structure: the heat is collected from the specific internal system through a cooling line, and then a liquid –liquid plate heat exchanger provides the heat to a second cooling line. A passive external radiator was selected as an air-liquid heat exchanger to dissipate the heat into the external environment.

Figure 2-1: Block diagram of the thermal control system.

The external radiator design consisted of long pipes with fins which are used to increase the contact area between the air and the radiator (see Figure 2-2).

Figure 2-2: Example of a pipe with fins.

The calculation of the necessary external area (fins included) of the pipe, and, consequently the length of the pipe, depends on the following formula:

Equation 6

$$Q = K_{global} A (T_{fluid1} - T_{fluid2})$$

where Q is the thermal load, A is the exchange area, T_{fluid1} is the average temperature of the coolant, T_{fluid2} is the average temperature of the air, and K_{global} is a global heat transfer coefficient. K_{global} de-

depends on the thermal properties of the two fluids, the mass flows of the two fluids and the characteristic of the solid materials. Some estimates of coefficient K_{global} are usually provided by the industrial producers of these pipes. K_{global} values between 25-50 W/m² K are typical values for pipes with fins, considering water inside pipe and air for the external environment. When we assume $K_{global} = 25$ W/m² K and a temperature gradient of 5°C between the two fluids, the exchange area for the pipes with fins can be estimated as per Table 2-4.

Table 2-4: Estimates of required external radiator exchange areas.

External radiator	Thermal load	Estimated area of pipe with fins
AMS	5500 W	44 m ²
ISPR	1100 W	9 m ²
LED	2600 W	21 m ²

After further consideration, the design, as described in section 2.1 and 2.2, was selected. This reduces the number of buffer tanks, plate heat exchangers and external heat rejection units which are required. Note that the thermal load values used in section 2.1 and 2.2 are those from Table 2-4, with an added margin of 20%. For the LED panels the thermal load was later increased by 1.1 kW to account for a higher power consumption, and hence thermal load, per panel.

As mentioned above, a trade-off was made between having two or three internal thermal loops, with the former ultimately being selected. Additionally, the initial design incorporated passive radiators, which have been replaced in the final design by an active free cooler. A third alternative for the external heat rejection was briefly considered. This third option would have transferred the heat to probes which would be buried in the ice, which would have provided a stable, low temperature environment for heat rejection. This option was rejected because of environmental protection regulations, as well as the potential issue of the ice melting around the probes, resulting in air pockets and diminished heat rejection capability.

8.4 Subsystem key values

Table 2-5 presents the key subsystem values for the thermal subsystem. Note that the mass value includes an estimation of the coolant mass, as well as the mass of the structural profiles making up the thermal system rack.

Table 2-5: Key values of the thermal subsystem.

	Mass	Peak power	Power day - nominal mode	Power night - nominal mode
Mobile Test Facility	405 kg	2300 W	1900 W	1100 W
Neumayer Station III	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Spares, consumables, tools	29.7 kg	N/A	N/A	N/A
TOTAL	434.7 kg	2300 W	1900 W	1100 W

9 Thermal System Operations

9.1 Nominal operations

9.1.1 Automatic actions

During nominal operations, the ARGUS system will operate four three-way valves, one per thermal loop, in order to maintain coolant temperature within a user-defined range.

Below, the relevant set points, sensor measurements and actuator inputs are provided for each of the four loops.

Dehumidifier thermal loop / AMS thermal loop:

The AMS thermal loop manages the temperature and flow of coolant through a dehumidifier, which is used to cool the air from the FEG. As such, the set points for the air in the FEG determine whether or not cooling is required. In case the conditions in the FEG are within the specified boundaries, the thermal system will take actions to maintain the coolant temperature within the desired range.

Set points	Temperature		RH	
	Nominal	Range (+/-)	Nominal	Range (+/-)
FEG air – day	21	3	70%	5%
FEG air - night	19	3	70%	5%
Coolant in	8	2	-	-

Based on the initial set points, the following control inputs have been defined as responses to specific measurement values. Note that a control input of 0% (e.g. valve is closed) results in the thermal loop not rejecting heat via the plate heat exchangers, and thereby causing a gradual increase in coolant temperature. Alternatively, a control input of 100% (e.g. valve is fully opened) results in maximum heat rejection.

Measurement (Temp 6)	6°C	6,5°C	7°C	7,5°C	8°C	8,5°C	9°C	9,5°C	10°C
Control * (Cool Valve 4: AMS)	0%	12,5%	25%	37,5%	50%	62,5%	75%	87,5%	100%

* Note that the coolant temperature range is a set point and can be increased or decreased later on. Dependent on the actual range, the specific change in actuation per discrete temperature step needs to be adjusted.

ISPR thermal loop:

The ISPR thermal loop has to provide coolant with a temperature and flow rate similar to what is provided on the ISS. Coolant temperature is controlled by operating a three-way valve to adjust the amount of heat which is transferred to the plate heat exchanger, similar to the AMS thermal loop.

The flow rate is constant, though manual adjustment is possible if necessary for some reason.

The nominal temperature and range set points are listed below, along with an overview of control inputs as a function of actual measured temperature.

	Temperature	
Set points	Nominal	Range (+/-)
Coolant in	18	2

Measurement (Temp 8)	16°C	16,5°C	17°C	17,5°C	18°C	18,5°C	19°C	19,5°C	20°C
Control * (Cool Valve 2: ISPR)	0%	12,5%	25%	37,5%	50%	62,5%	75%	87,5%	100%

LED thermal loop:

The LED thermal loop and the ISPR thermal loop are connected to a single plate heat exchanger. As such, both loops should have the same coolant (inflow) temperature set points. Consequently, the same control inputs are foreseen for the LED thermal loop valve as for the ISPR thermal loop valve, according to the measurements of the corresponding temperature sensors.

	Temperature	
Set points	Nominal	Range (+/-)
Coolant in	18	2

Measurement (Temp 10)	16°C	16,5°C	17°C	17,5°C	18°C	18,5°C	19°C	19,5°C	20°C
Control * (Cool Valve 3: LED)	0%	12,5%	25%	37,5%	50%	62,5%	75%	87,5%	100%

External thermal loop:

The external loop manages the heat transfer from the plate heat exchangers to the free cooler mounted on the MTF roof. By operating the three-way valve, the amount of cooling can be in- or decreased. As with the other loops, the operation of the valve will be based on the temperature of the coolant.

The set points and the control inputs are presented in the tables below.

	Temperature	
Set points	Nominal	Range (+/-)
Coolant in	4	2

Measurement (Temp 1)	2°C	2,5°C	3°C	3,5°C	4°C	4,5°C	5°C	5,5°C	6°C
-----------------------------	-----	-------	-----	-------	-----	-------	-----	-------	-----

Control * (Cool Valve 1: FREE)	0%	12,5%	25%	37,5%	50%	62,5%	75%	87,5%	100%
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9.1.2 Operator actions

- Daily check of thermal system parameters (e.g. pump flow rates) in the CDHS display screens
- Weekly check of pressure gauges and thermometers
- Periodic (e.g. monthly) visual check of the free cooler to identify potential icing problems

9.2 Off-Nominal operations

9.2.1 Automatic actions

- Display of warnings if pressure measurements fall outside of acceptable range (0.5 – 1.5 bar)
- Display of warnings if coolant temperatures fall outside of set point range
- Display of warnings if pumps produce an error message

9.2.2 Operator actions

- Check for leaks, repair leaks, and refill the system if the pressure drops below 0.5 bar
- Check pumps and valves if pressure exceeds 1.5 bar
- Check pumps, valves and free cooler if coolant temperatures fall outside of set point range
- Check pumps if the pumps produce an error message

- If pump is damaged, replace the pump and determine if damaged pump can be repaired
- If valve or valve actuator is damaged, replace the damaged part

9.3 Maintenance and spares

- Spare pumps (1 spare per installed pump, 6 in total)
- Spare valves (1 per installed valve, 4 in total)
- Spare valve actuator (1 per installed valve, 4 in total)
- Spare coolant (Tyfocor-L and Tyfoxit)

9.4 Preparation for shipment

Describe what actions should be conducted to prepare the subsystem for shipment (e.g. to Antarctica). What items need to be disassembled (if any) for shipment, what items should be further secured and any other special shipping requirements.

9.4.1 Pre-shipment activities

- Shut-down thermal system power
- Empty fluid lines
- Fixate valve positions
- Remove and package free cooler for separate transfer (TBC)
- Remove external piping
- Remove pump control boxes
- Remove valve actuators

9.4.2 In-situ assembly and pre-operations activities

- Mount the free cooler on the MTF with the crane
- Install the piping connection between the free cooler and the thermal system rack
- Install pump control boxes
- Install valve actuators
- Release fixed valve positions
- Fill the fluid lines and release trapped air from the fluid lines
- Connect any disconnected power and data lines (e.g. free cooler, pump control boxes)

10 Thermal System Parts list

The parts listed here are only those parts for which spares will be acquired, or are being considered.

Table 5-1: Parts list for the thermal control subsystem.

Element/Part	Qty	Spares	Manufacturer	Part Number
SERVICE SECTION				
Thermal system rack				
Pump	4	4	Wilo	Wilo Stratos 25/1-8
Pump	1	1	Wilo	Wilo Stratos 25/1-10
Pump	1	1	Wilo	Wilo Stratos 30/1-10
Three-way valve actuator	4	4	Samson	Samson Type Trovis 5724-810
Pressure sensor	4	4	Samson	Samson Typ 3994-0052

11 Design lessons learned

- Account for possible maintenance and repair actions earlier in the design and define dynamic envelopes to allow for crew handling operations.
- Establish more communication and more regular progress meetings with subcontractors

References

Janquart, D. (Undated) "Duct design", online presentation, url:
<http://www.biasew.net/pdf/ductdesign.pdf>

Hui, S. C. M. (2008) "Air-side Systems: Air Duct Design", online presentation, url:
http://www.mech.hku.hk/bse/bbse3006/bbse3006_1011_03-airside03.pdf

Stamper, E., Koral, R. L., (1979) Handbook of Air Conditioning, Heating and Ventilating

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Executive summary

This document provides a summary of the results of the EDEN ISS ISPR design activity conducted up to December 2016. This design includes details from all ISPR subsystems. It is important to note that the design of the ISPR system has partially evolved during the manufacturing and testing phase, especially at the subsystem level. The design study also generated a number of important supplementary reference documents including subsystem block diagrams and detailed 'subsystem calculators' which detail all subsystem components, quantities, estimated mass, volume and power in addition to a first detailed estimation of project spares and consumables. Although extracts of this information are included directly in the report, the current drafts of these documents should be referenced as separate files.

The EDEN ISS ISPR design study has proven the feasibility of the ISPR system, and demonstrated that the facility will serve as a valuable resource to progress toward ISS exploitation.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
EDR	European Drawer Rack	MTF	Mobile Test facility
C&DH	Command and Data Handling	P/L	Payload
DI	Deionized	QD	Quick disconnect
EI	Experimental inserts	TCCS	Trace contaminants control system
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	TEC	Thermo-electric cooler
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	THC	Temperature and humidity control system
ISS	International Space Station	TRL	Technology readiness level
MCCS	Major constituents control system		

1 Top-level design overview

In this Chapter the overall ISPR general system concept is introduced, highlighting the characteristics that make it a precursor of an ISS European Drawer Rack EDR II P/L. The different subsystems are then detailed in the dedicated sub-Chapters.

The main objective of the laboratory and Antarctica ISPR system demonstration is to advance the TRL of the plant growth facility technologies, in view of a near term experiment on the ISS. The facility shall represent an increment with respect to current flight capabilities represented by the NASA Veggie system, mainly in terms of:

- Higher available growth surface (0.5-1,0 m² range)
- Longer production cycle possible by complete nutrient solution circulation (and not only watering of substrate with slow release fertilization)
- Robust and reliable safe and high quality food production (while Veggie control capability may be considered limited)
- Taller crop can be accommodated (up to 60 cm available for tall growth chamber shoot zone)

In order to target a feasible ISS exploitation scenario, the system is being designed as an EDR II payload. EDR II is a European rack, capable of hosting up to three experimental inserts (EIs). EDEN ISS ISPR will be modular and capable of operating either:

- as a single EI, ¼ rack, to test critical subsystems (i.e. nutrient delivery system)
- as a single EI, ½ rack, to test a complete system with one growth chamber (of incremental complexity)
- as multiple EIs, ¾ or full rack, with up to three independently controlled growth chambers (note that the current design baselines two growth chambers)

Figure 1 reports an image of EDR II Engineering Model, EDR II Experimental Inserts available volume and EDEN ISS ISPR system preliminary concept, clearly designed as precursor of ISS European Drawer Rack EDR II plant growth P/L.

The lower Chapter of the rack is dedicated to the interfaces (power, data and cooling water) with the Mobile Test Facility. Above this Chapter are placed the interfaces between the rack and the plant growth facility, exactly as for EDR II EIs interface panels. In the central portion of the system, the following P/L drawers are accommodated (see dedicated Chapters for more details):

- Power, Command and Data Handling Module
- Nutrient Storage and Distribution Module
- Growth chamber Modules (1 for short plants, 1 for taller plants), including each chamber dedicated air management systems, root modules and crop shoot-zone volumes
- Illumination Modules (one for each growth chamber)

In the top portion of the rack, a panel for manual monitoring and control of some of the rack key functional parameters will be housed, together with a storage drawer.

Figure 1: EDR II Engineering Model (top left); EDR II Experimental Inserts available volume (top right); EDEN ISS ISPR system 3D drawing, developed as precursor of ISS European Drawer Rack EDR II P/L

1.1 ISPR system interfaces with Mobile Test Facility (MTF)

The main interfaces identified between the ISPR system interfaces and the MTF are summarized as follows.

1.1.1 Mechanical interfaces with MTF

Rack dimensions – see Figure 2:

- Width: **1060 mm** (however clearance to the sides is required for operating the drawers)
- Depth: **800 mm** (not including handles and drawer harness in the front - **protruding max additional 100 mm**; not including bracket in the back, currently not foreseen)
- Height: **1950 mm** (not including elements for fixation to the ground; not including removable hangers for movement with crane)

Fixation system /interface definition

- Mechanical fixation:
 - via 4x M8 screws through the bottom front aluminum profile to the MTF stainless steel pavement framework
 - via 1x M8 screw through an L piece (mounted on the ISPR left wall horizontal aluminum profile) to the MTF structure (see Figure 3)

Access for maintenance/inspection

- Main structure (ISPR)
 - Maintenance can be performed always from the front side (eventually dismantling the drawers) – see maintenance access ports in Figure 4
 - No lateral inspection ports are foreseen
 - No sliding mounting is foreseen
- Drawers access
 - Drawers are completely removable. A clearance of 730 mm (not including clearance for the operator) in front of the rack is necessary – see Figure 5
 - Plant cultivation drawers are accessible for operations without complete removal from inspection port on the left side (right side blocked by MTF wall for one of the chambers) – see Figure 6

Figure 2: ISPR Envelope (all values in mm) when operative

Figure 3: ISPR Mechanical Interfaces position

Figure 4: ISPR Rack Nominal Maintenance Access Clearance (example for one drawer, analogue for all drawers) - (all values in mm)

Figure 5: ISPR Drawer Removal Clearance (all values in mm)

Figure 6: ISPR Drawer Maintenance Access

1.1.2 Power interfaces with MTF

- Electrical IF
 - Type: 230 VAC, 10 A
 - 230 VAC connector (plug) is an industrial 3 contacts 16A plug
 - Position: rack bottom-front side – see Figure 7
- 116-126 VDC: no need identified, not to be provided to ISPR
- 230 VAC to 24, 12 and 5 VDC as well as 24VAC conversion within ISPR:
 - Design and procurement is responsibility of TASI
 - DLR shall provide AC/DC converter models eventually used in FEG, in an effort to increase commonality and have common spare parts
- ISPR power budget:
 - Peak mode: 1.5 kW peak 1, 0.9 kW peak 2
 - *Remark 1: peak 1 power is calculated with all equipment on at maximum power*
 - *Remark 2: peak 2 power is calculated with 600 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination and 160 $\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{-h}$ water vapor production simultaneously from both growth chambers a– staggered production and/or staggered photoperiods and/or lower light demanding crops will reduce considerably these peak values (assumed at least 35% reduction)*
 - Nominal mode: 0.65 kW
 - *Nominal mode is calculated assuming 600 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to tall crops and 300 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to short crops*

Figure 7: ISPR Power interface position

1.1.3 Cooling interfaces with MTF

- Cooling water inlet: 190 kg/h flow and temperature of 16 – 20°C (pump not included in ISPR)
- Cooling water outlet: 25°C worst case (max water inlet temperature, peak power, no dissipation to environment)
- IF type: Self-locking ½” quick disconnect (QD) female Swagelok SS-QC8-B1-810
- IF position: ISPR main utilities panel (rack bottom-front side) (panel mounted) – see Figure 8

Figure 8: ISPR Cooling interface position

1.1.4 Data interfaces with MTF

- IFs type:
 - LabVIEW system LAN socket – refer to NI cDAQ™-9137 datasheet
 - 63 sensors, 1 Hz, 16 bit estimation
 - 3 cameras, 2 MB/picture, 5 pictures/day
- IFs position: ISPR main utilities panel (rack bottom-front side) – see Figure 13

Figure 9: ISPR Data interface position

1.1.5 Air exchange interfaces with MTF

The ISPR volume is connected with the Service Chapter environment in multiple positions, thus Service Chapter environmental parameters are needed to model gas exchange:

- Temperature and RH range (incl. different modes):
 - Day values are T = 21°C, RH = 25-30%
 - Night values are T = 18°C, RH = 25-30%
- CO₂ concentration range
 - Nominal values ≥400 ppm (<750 ppm, FEG value)

The ISPR air volume is connected to the MTF volume at the following locations:

- Growth chambers air inlet (see Figure 10):
 - Position: Growth chamber drawer front panel
 - Typology: 20 mm x 50 mm 10 µm stainless steel grid
- ISPR rack air outlet (see Figure 10):
 - Position: ISPR main utilities panel (rack bottom-front side) as well as multiple locations (rack not sealed)
 - Typology: multiple openings

Figure 10: ISPR Air exchange interfaces position. The air is ejected from the ISPR to the MTF through multiple openings (not sealed environment)

1.2 Structure Subsystem

Refer to Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram and to section 2.2 for components details.

A general overview of the main structure-related aspects is provided in Figure 11.

The main ISPR structure is composed from Bosch Rexroth 45x45mm aluminum profiles to favor implementation of multiple configurations in the rack development process, while limiting the unit mass. This flexibility has been required by the necessity of the system of being used as a research and development tool. Removable aluminum panels enclose the profiles frame in order to provide a barrier to the MTF environment while allowing easy accessibility for maintenance activities.

The structure is sized to be close to an ISS International Standard Payload Rack. From the front, the rack presents a structure extremely common to the ISS rack also from the visual point of view.

Figure 11: ISPR primary structure photos with (left) and without (right) removable lateral panels

1.3 Illumination Subsystem

Refer to Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram and to Chapter 2.2 for components details.

The ISPR illumination system will provide the same performance and capabilities of the FEG system, with the same shape factor. The LED panel final specifications are the following:

- LED illumination unit (2 units plus 1 spare):
 - Monolithic element (envelope < 500x210x89 mm)
 - Water cooled (1/4" BSP female fitting or 10mm OD quick-lock fitting) via embedded cold plate
 - Same light "recipe" as that of the FEG
 - Working at 230 VAC
 - Dimmable from 600 to 100 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (with each wavelength independently controlled) via Ethernet SEA 9715 IF (into CompactDAQ module), including health status monitoring
 - With lateral mechanical IF that shall allow mounting to illumination drawer structure via 8xM6 screws
 - Including ballast
 - Power ON/OFF condition controlled by TASI (via LabVIEW acted relays)
- Illumination module structure (for fixation to ISPR mechanical IFs)
- Small video camera (video data management to be investigated)
 - One Visible light camera for each drawer
 - One modified UOF camera for the GCS illumination drawer (left illumination drawer)
- Polycarbonate transparent ($\approx 85\%$ eff in the visible, cut at 400 nm) plate as division from the plant shoot zone is part of the growth chamber drawers

The LED illumination unit is responsibility of Heliospectra, while the others are procured by TASI. The illumination module final photo is given in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Illumination module preliminary representation, including interfaces to growth chamber (GC)

1.4 Atmosphere Management Subsystem and Thermal Control Subsystem

Refer to Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram and to section 2.2 for components details. Each growth volume will have an independent air management system. The air management system will include:

- Temperature and humidity control system (THC)
- Major constituents control system (MCCS), managing the environmental pressure, as well as O₂ and CO₂ concentration
- Trace contaminants and microbiological control system (TCCS), removing organic gaseous contaminants (i.e. ethylene) as well as filtering out microbes and viruses.

Figure 13: Overall air management system conceptual block diagram (see section 2.1 for detailed diagram)

The air management system has been preliminary designed in order to be easily accessible and maintainable. Further upgrade of the selected technologies is also possible in this way.

The overall system preliminary block diagram is reported in Figure 13. Figure 14 reports a schematic of the technologies along the circulating air path as well as the preliminary distribution of the components within the growth chamber module volume. The commercial components preliminary identified and sized for each technology are then summarized in the following paragraphs. The system is described in more detail as follows.

Figure 14: Schematic of the technologies along the circulating air path (middle); preliminary distribution of the components within the growth chamber module volume, with redundant THC modules and TCCS modules per each chamber (left); THC module HW photo when installed (right)

Temperature and humidity control

The air extracted from the shoot-zone volume is cooled by a thermo-electric cooler (TEC, using Peltier effect) to remove sensible heat loads as well as latent heat loads through condensation of water vapor. The water vapor is then collected by gravity in a custom made recipient, and then pumped through a UV-LED based disinfection system to the DI water reservoir within the Nutrient Storage Module. The over-cooled air is then reheated with a PTC heater. Both the TEC and PTC heater are insulated (i.e. with 2 mm thick Armaflex) to guarantee efficiency. The TEC is an air to water heat exchanger, and the heat collected at the water side is removed by cooling water with conditions as specified in Chapter 1.1. Air temperature and humidity are monitored via a single multi-parametric sensor at the air extraction Chapter, in order to provide feedback to the active control system.

Major constituents control

For oxygen and carbon dioxide concentration control, a semi-open loop strategy is implemented. In normal operations the shoot-zone air is circulated in a closed loop until the O₂ concentration rises to the 24% selected threshold (i.e. not acceptable fire risk). Then air is exchanged with the (MTF by electro-valves) to equalize O₂ concentration and reach back normal levels. CO₂ is added as needed via a dedicated 500g CO₂ bottle. However, the same strategy adopted for O₂ concentration control could be also applied, depending on MTF nominal CO₂ concentration (when the CO₂ level is too low in the ISPR, air is exchanged).

In order to limit the phenomenon of rejection to the MTF of the air just injected from the MTF, injection is performed only from one of the redundant air management lines and rejection from the other one.

Analysis was performed by EnginSoft to consolidate the detailed design of the air exchange surfaces in order to guarantee:

- Minimized air pockets within the shoot-zone volume (priority 1), in order to provide the most uniformity of gas distribution within the shoot-zone
- Efficient air turn-over (priority 2)

Trace contaminants and microbiological control

After passing through the THC elements, air passes through a 0.2 µm membrane for filtering of bacteria, viruses and particulate. An additional passive filter for organic contaminants removal is then placed downstream, prior to the reintroduction of the air within the growth chamber shoot-zone volume.

Given the periodic air exchanges between the MTF crewed environment and the shoot-zone volume (as per semi-open loop strategy described above), the following precautions for limiting cross contamination have been implemented:

- Air collected from the MTF is introduced upstream the THC (so to change immediately its humidity and temperature if the differences are considerable)
- Air rejected to the MTF is first processed through both THC and TCCS (to reduce system water loss and avoid rejection of contaminants to the outer environment)

This precautions have constrained the possible position of the fans, which need to be necessarily placed downstream the THC and upstream the TCCS, with air injection from the MTF upstream the fan of line 1 and air rejection to the MTF downstream the TCCS of line 2.

1.5 Nutrient Delivery Subsystem

The Nutrient Delivery System (NDS) is divided among multiple modules (ISPR drawers):

- The nutrient storage and distribution module/drawer, containing the reservoirs (stock solutions, acid/base, DI water, nutrient solution), the delivery pumps and the UV-C condensate bactericidal system
- The root module within each growth chamber module/drawer, containing the growth substrate, its container and the sensors and actuators needed to guarantee appropriate distribution of water and nutrient solution within the different area of the substrate.

Figure 15: Nutrient storage and distribution module/drawer (left); root module (right)

The NDS block diagram is reported in Figure 16. Either DI water or nutrient solution can be delivered to the root modules. The block diagram is explained as follows. Refer to Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram and to Chapter 2.2 for components details.

Figure 16: Nutrient Delivery System Conceptual Block Diagram (see Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram)

Nutrient storage and distribution

DI water is used in case of salt accumulation within the root module (EC increment within the substrate or porous elements cleaning to prevent clogging). The DI water pH is monitored and controlled by acid/base injection. The nutrient solution EC and pH is monitored and controlled by water or stock

solution (from dedicated reservoirs) injection. Injection is allowed by LabVIEW® controlled piston pumps. An electromagnetic stirrer allows homogeneous mixing of the nutrient solution within the reservoir. No temperature control is foreseen (only monitoring).

Concentrated solution tanks are flexible, replaceable (self-locking QD), stored with the concentrated nutrient solution. Water and nutrient reservoirs are bellow tanks, with a Teflon bellow.

Water recovery

Condensate recovered from the THC is passed through a membrane contactor (gas trap) to separate the air from the water flow and then filtered with an HEPA filter 0.2 µm prior to re-introducing it into the water reservoir.

Root module

Particular attention is given to the root module. Porous stainless steel plates are used for nutrient solution distribution and reclamation (in case of over watering) throughout multiple (4) substrate pillows. The plates are passivated to favor priming of the pores. Substrate moisture, EC and temperature are monitored via sensors connected to a common data downlink port on the growth chamber wall. Two moisture sensors per pillow will be used. EC will be monitored powering only one sensor each time, to prevent interference.

Electro-valves, connected to a common power bus, regulate the water flow (with a single outlet and inlet per each root module) through the multiple porous plates Figure 17.

Figure 17: Root module main interfaces and elements

Substrate height will be 50 mm for all selected crops. Quantity of substrate used will vary for each crop (i.e. 1 L per tomato plant, 0.5 L per lettuce plant) by reducing the amount of plants for substrate block. Low density material that shall not get wet easily (i.e. pumice) will be used to avoid having voids in the root module. Multiple substrates were tested (also sensors were calibrated and their behavior studied for each substrate, because they behave differently). See Figure 18 for some example.

Figure 18: Examples of substrates that will be tested – a mix of pumice and zeolite soil is selected

The baseline solution for the root module sees 4 (four) porous plates for nutrient solution distribution, placed parallel to the ground, on top of the substrate. Additional 4 (four) porous plates are placed in the bottom of the root module and, by removing nutrient solution for direct recirculation via piston pumps, they simultaneously recall air from the shoot-zone volume allowing aeration of the substrate Figure 19. Figure 20 reports a 3D preliminary drawing of this solution. Figure 21 reports the expected water distribution gradient.

Figure 19: Root Module I operation schematic

Figure 20: Root Module preliminary drawing and main elements identification. 4 (four) porous plates for nutrient solution distribution, placed parallel to the ground, on top of the substrate. Additional 4 (four) porous plates are placed in the bottom of the root module and, by removing nutrient solution for direct recirculation via piston pumps, they simultaneously recall air from the shoot-zone volume allowing aeration of the substrate

Figure 21: Root Module substrate expected moisture profile. The moisture is expected to be at a maximum close to the bottom surface, and decrease toward the top. The action of the porous plates are expected to reduce the vertical gradient

1.6 Command and Data Handling Subsystem

The Command and Data Handling (C&DH) System is housed in the Power, Command and Data Handling module/drawer (Figure 22). Refer to §2.1 for detailed block diagram and to Chapter 2.2 for components details.

Figure 22: Power, Command and Data Handling drawer conceptual drawing (up) and final HW photo (down)

The general conceptual schematic of the C&DH system is given in Figure 23. Data are collected from the P/L drawer sensors into a NI Compact DAQ (cDAQ) board via dedicated I/O modules. Commands are generated by feedback control implemented within the cDAQ controller, and transferred to power relays via internal Digital Output (DO) modules. The different programs can be loaded onto the cDAQ board via rack-external signal, generated by a LabVIEW based computer and transmitted by LAN interface. The same interface is used for telemetry downlink.

Figure 23: Command and Data Handling system concept (see Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram)

1.7 Power Distribution and Control Subsystem

Figure 24 reports the Power Distribution and Control System conceptual schematic. Refer to Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram and to Chapter 2.2 for components details.

Power will be delivered from the MTF to the ISPR via 230 VAC, 16 A electrical IF (230 VAC industrial connector plug - IEC 309). 230 VAC to 24 VDC conversion will be provided within the ISPR volume, under the responsibility of TASI. DLR shall provide AC/DC converters models eventually used in the FEG, in an effort to increase commonality and have common spare parts.

The power will be then distributed to the different utilities via the commanded relays placed in the Command and Data Handling module/drawer (Figure 22).

Moreover, manual override of key utilities (i.e. illumination, irrigation) on/off conditions will be possible, especially to favor maintenance.

Figure 24: Power Distribution and Control System conceptual schematic (see Chapter 2.1 for detailed block diagram).

The preliminary power budget has been estimated as follows:

- Peak mode: 1.5 kW peak 1, 0.9 kW peak 2
 - Remark 1: peak 1 power is calculated with all equipment on at maximum power
 - Remark 2: peak 2 power is calculated with 600 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination and 160 $\text{g}/\text{m}^2\text{-h}$ water vapor production simultaneously from both growth chambers a– staggered production and/or staggered photoperiods and/or lower light demanding crops will reduce considerably these peak values (assumed at least 35% reduction)
- Nominal mode: 0.65 kW
 - Nominal mode is calculated assuming 600 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to tall crops and 300 $\mu\text{moles}/\text{m}^2\text{-s}$ illumination to short crops

2 Detailed design

2.1 Block diagram(s)

The complete ISPR system block diagram is provided in Figure 25. The block diagram Chapters are showed and expanded in the following figures.

Figure 25: ISPR system block diagram

Figure 26: Growth chamber (including Shoot zone, Root module, redundant Trace contaminant control system, redundant Temperature and humidity control system) and Illumination drawers block diagram

Figure 27: Main utilities module block diagram

Figure 28: Power, command and data handling drawer block diagram

Figure 29: Nutrient Distribution System Drawer block diagram

2.1.1 Power Distribution and Control Subsystem detailed Schematic

The following figures illustrate in details the key lines connecting each subsystem of the ISPR with the PC&DH system (both data from sensors, depicted in orange, and commands given via relays, in green) as well as the Main Utilities Module interfaces with the MTF detail (see next page).

Figure 30: PC&DH Detailed Schematic - Power Command and Data Handling Drawer

Figure 31: PC&DH Detailed Schematic – Main Utilities Module (Interfaces to MTF)

2.2 System sizing/analyses

The main calculations used in the sizing of the various components of the system are reported in the following subChapters.

2.2.1 Air management system sizing

Required heating and cooling power calculation via psychrometric analyses is reported in the table below for each growth chamber, in the worst case conditions.

A cooling power of 120 W is sufficient to cover the shoot zone dehumidification needs.

A heating power of 60 W is sufficient to cover the dehumidified air re-heating needs.

Table 1: Required heating and cooling power calculation

CHAMBERS COOLING/HEATING POWER EVALUATION				
	Light-period, worst hot		Dark-period, worst cold	
	Short GC	Tall GC	Short GC	Tall GC
http://www.sugartech.co.za/psychro/				
Shoot zone air thermal management				
Loads (assumed exchange with MTF negligible)				
Sensible heat from LED lamp with margin [W]	45,9	45,9	0,0	0,0
Latent heat from plants [W]	24,1	24,1	0,0	0,0
Sensible heat sequestered by plant evapotranspiration [W]	-24,1	-24,1	0,0	0,0
Sensible heat from fan [W]	10	10	10	10
Sensible heat from sensors [W]	5	5	5	5
Total sensible heat introduced [W]	36,8	36,8	15,0	15,0
Total latent heat introduced [W]	24,1	24,1	0,0	0,0
Target				
Temperature [°C]	23	26	22	22
Humidity [%]	70	70	70	70
Air water vapour [g/kg] - calculate with table	12,315	14,795		
Enthalpy [kJ/kg] - calculate with table	54,44	63,84		
Volume exchangers [vol/min]	6	3,43	6	3,43
Volumetric Flow [m3/h]	34,56	34,56	34,56	34,56
Flow speed in shoot zone [cm/s] - target 1-20	6	3,43	6	3,43
Volumetric Flow [kg/s]	0,01176	0,01176	0,01176	0,01176
Volumetric Flow [CFM]	20,34	20,34	20,34	20,34
Temperature variation [°C]	3,09	3,09	1,26	1,26
Air water vapour variation [g/kg]	0,91	0,91	0,00	0,00
Air inlet (target)				
Temperature [°C]	21,45	24,45	21,37	21,37
Air water vapour [g/kg]	11,86	14,34	0,00	0,00
Humidity [%] - calculate with table	74	74,5		
Enthalpy [kJ/kg] - calculate with table	51,635	61,103		
Air outlet				
Temperature [°C]	24,55	27,55	22,63	22,63
Air water vapour [g/kg]	12,77	15,25	0,00	0,00
Humidity [%] - calculate with table	66	65,7		
Enthalpy [kJ/kg] - calculate with table	57,172	66,528		
Dehumidification/cooling				
Air water vapour [g/kg]	11,86	14,34	0,00	0,00
Temperature [°C] - calculate with table	16,7	19,6	21,37	21,37
Humidity [%]	100%	100%		
Enthalpy [kJ/kg] - calculate with table	46,906	56,05		
Cooling power [W]	117,48	118,67	15,00	15,00
Heating				
Heating power [W]	55,61	59,42	0,00	0,00

The calculation was based on the assumption of providing from 1 to 20 cm/s of air flow through the canopy. Since a constraint of common air loop design between tall crops and short crops growth chambers was placed to reduce development cost, the two growth chambers present different volume exchange rates. The tall crops growth chamber provides 3.63 volume exchanges per minute, while the smaller unit provides 6 exchanges per minute. In order to allow this to happen, both chambers have to provide a flow circulation of about 20 CFM.

Load to water cooling loop calculation is reported in the table below. An outlet temperature below 25°C is assured by the presented analyses.

Table 2: Load to water cooling loop calculation

HEAT REMOVAL WATER LOOP EVALUATION		
Cooling water data		
Inlet cooling water temperature [°C]	20	Requirement
Inlet cooling total water flow [kg/h]	190	Requirement
Power to be removed - worst case [W]	434,1	Claculated from points 1, 2 and 3 below
Outlet cooling water temperature - worst case [°C]	22	Calculated
1. TEC Data (DL-120-24-00-00-00)		
Hot-cold side worst case ΔT during operation [°C]	4,3	
Efficiency at worst case ΔT	100%	From DL-120-24-00-00-00 datasheet
Worst case power consumption with 10% margin	258	Assuming peak growth in both chambers
2. LED lamp data (resized from 0.6 tp 0.24 m2)		
AC power to the lamp [W]	100,0	Resized from PDR report
AC/DC power supply power loss [W]	10,0	Resized from PDR report
DC voltage to DC current power loss [W]	9,2	Resized from PDR report
LED conversion power loss [W]	39,6	Resized from PDR report
LED optics power loss [W]	4,0	Resized from PDR report
Light spillage power loss [W]	7,6	Resized from PDR report
Power to cold plate per lamp [W]	62,8	Assuming no light spillage in ISPR
Power to growth chamber per lamp [W]	37,2	Calculated from above
Total power to cold plate water loop [W]	125,6	assuming 2 lamps simultaneous on at 100%
3. 230VAC to 24VDC Power Supplies		
Total power conversion [W]	500	Worst case assumption
Power conversion efficiency [%]	10	Assumption
Power to be rejected [W]	50	Calculated
Acceptable ΔT [°C]	10	Assumption
Necessary FAN air flow rate [CFM]	10,4	Necessary only if air cooling is selected

2.2.2 Nutrient delivery system sizing

Multiple analyses were performed to size the key NDS elements. The analysis with higher impact on the presented budgets are those related to water and nutrient reservoir sizing.

The short growth chamber reservoir needs have been calculated using Lettuce as reference crop.

The tall growth chamber reservoir needs have been calculated using Tomatoes as reference crop.

The main input data have been derived from the 2004 NASA Baseline Values and Assumption Document (BVAD) and are reported in the following tables.

Assuming the capability to recover 90% of humidity condensate and reuse it in the nutrient solution feed water, the following resources are needed for each growth chamber for one full growth cycle:

- Short crops
 - Water consumption: 2 L per 0.24 m² growth chamber per growth cycle
 - Concentrated nutrient stock solution consumption: 1.8 L per growth chamber per growth cycle
- Tall crops
 - Water consumption: 10 L per .24 m² growth chamber per growth cycle
 - Concentrated nutrient stock solution consumption: 15 L per growth chamber per growth cycle

A design constraint for allowing exchange of the reservoirs only at the end of one full growth cycle for the short crops growth chamber, the following reservoirs dimensions have been selected:

- Water tank: 5 L (2.1 times small growth chamber needs)
- Concentrated nutrient stock solution tank: 4 L (2.1 times small growth chamber needs)

Based on the above reported considerations, and considering the Antarctica experimental campaign as per what reported in Chapter 4, average and total ISPR water consumption was evaluated, and the results are reported in the table below.

Table 3: ISPR Water Consumption during all Antarctica experimental phase and average per week

Parameter	L/year	L/week
Nominal without margin (90% condensate recovery)	110.9	3.1
Nominal with margin (70% condensate recovery)	160.9	4.5
Worst case (no condensate recovery)	335.7	9.4

Table 4: Assumed data for water uptake (NASA BVAD)

Crop	Total Biomass (Edible + Inedible), Dry Basis [g _{dw} /m ² •d]		Metabolic Reactants and Products		
	nominal	high	Oxygen (O ₂) Production [g/m ² •d]	Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂) Uptake	Water (H ₂ O) Uptake / Transpiration
				[g/m ² •d]	[kg/m ² •d]
Tomato	23.17	37.8	26.36	36.24	2.77
Lettuce	7.30	7.9	7.78	10.70	1.77

Table 5: Assumed data for nutrient usage (NASA BVAD Table 4.2.10)

	Units	Soybean	Wheat	Potato	Lettuce
Water Usage per Dry Biomass	L/g _{dw}	0.32	0.13	0.15	0.34
Stock Usage per Dry Biomass	L/g _{dw}	0.026	0.021	0.022	0.034
Acid Usage per Dry Biomass ⁶⁶	g _{acid} /g _{dw}	0.0548	0.0744	0.0428	0.0618

Table 6: Assumed data for photoperiod, planting density and shoot zone temperature (NASA BVAD)

Crop	Nominal Photoperiod H ₀ [h/d]	Planting Density ⁷⁵ [plants/m ²]	Light Cycle Temperature, T _{LIGHT} [°C]	Dark Cycle Temperature, T _{DARK} ⁷⁶ [°C]
Dry Bean	12	7	26	22
Lettuce	16	19.2	23	23
Peanut	12	7	26	22
Rice	12	200	29	21
Soybean	12	35	26	22
Sweet Potato	18	16	28	22
Tomato	12	6.3	26	22
Wheat	20	720	23	23
White Potato	12	6.4	20	16

2.2.3 Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) need sizing

A plenty supply of CO₂ is a fundamental element to guarantee the plants growth. In the following, a total budget for the amount of CO₂ needed is evaluated. First, the amount of CO₂ needed for the plants growth has been taken into account, using the data from the BVAD 2015.

Then, in order to estimate the number of venting necessities for both chambers, the oxygen production rate has been calculated and, assuming a maximum amount of oxygen of 24% (for fire hazard), the frequencies of venting. With these, the amount of CO₂ lost for venting has been calculated (assuming a concentration of CO₂ in the chambers of 0,1% and outside the chamber of 0,02%).

Finally, the leakage was estimated assuming a maximum leak of 1% of the chambers volume per day.

Applying a margin of 20%, a total amount of 11,2 kg of CO₂ is foreseen to be needed; considering that it will be contained in bottles of 500 g of mass, there is an estimated need for 23 bottles of CO₂.

Table 7: Plants O₂ production and CO₂ consumption calculation (BVAD).

	Total per day (kg/d)		
	Tall Plants	Short Plants	Total
CO ₂ Uptake (per growth chamber)	0,01015	0,00300	0,01314
O ₂ Production (per growth chamber)	0,00738	0,00218	0,00956

Table 8: CO₂ needed mass calculation

Growth Volume of GCT (m ³)	0,272
Growth Volume of GCS (m ³)	0,126
Leakage (%Vol/d)	1%
Cycle (longest) (d)	90
Margins (%)	20%
Max O ₂ level (%)	24%
CO ₂ in atm. GC (%)	0,10%
CO ₂ external (%)	0,02%
Density CO ₂ (kg/m ³)	1,98
Density O ₂ (kg/m ³)	1,43
Amounts per Long Cycle	
Total leakage (kg)	0,708
Total Absorbed by plants (kg)	2,342
Oxygen prod rate (kg/d)	0,00956
Time between venting GCT (d)	1,219
Time between venting GCS (d)	0,565
Nr. Venting per Cycle GCT	73,8
Nr. Venting per Cycle GCS	159,3
CO ₂ lost per Venting GCT (kg)	0,000430
CO ₂ lost per Venting GCS (kg)	0,000199
Total Lost for venting (kg)	0,064
Total per Long Cycle (kg)	3,114
Total w/ Margins (kg)	3,737
Total CO₂ to bring (kg)	11,21
Bottles (500g)	23

2.3 Options and trades

Multiple options have been considered during this first year of design study.

The most important trade-offs performed are summarized as follows:

- Structure subsystem
 - Structure envelope (identical to EDR II rack vs minimal envelope reduction): minimal envelope reduction with respect to EDR II was selected for limited clearance within the MTF service Chapter; the reduction does not affect the space available for the EDR II like payloads, which are the key elements to be pushed for commonality with the on-orbit solutions
 - Structure shape (identical to EDR II vs flat rear Chapter): a flat back Chapter was selected for easier anchoring to the MTF structure; the loss of commonality with respect to EDR does not impact appeal of the rack when installed in the MTF
 - Structure technology (common to EDR II vs Rexroth aluminium profiles): Rexroth aluminium profiles were selected for cost compatibility and to allow multiple configurations to be implemented during the research and development effort
- Air management system
 - Closed air loop (including oxygen removal via physic-chemical methods) against semi-closed air loop (periodically flushing of growth chamber atmosphere with filtered MTF air): a semi-open loop was selected since the envelope constraints did not allow implementation of a closed loop; moreover, the closed loop would add an additional complexity which is not likely to be implemented in next generation space greenhouses
- Nutrient delivery system:
 - Circulating nutrient solution was selected against circulating DI water with slow release fertilizer in substrate, since flexibility toward growth of demanding crops was preferred
 - Porous system nutrient delivery was selected against aeroponics for technological issues that were not solved within the preliminary design phase with respect to aeroponics, such as:
 - spray flow speed in micro-g is complex to manage: too slow may form a water film on the roots reducing oxygenation, too fast may break roots; nutrient solution time-effect on sprayers adds complexity
 - excess water removal to be performed by suction and water separation from air:
 - water separation unit is bulky (nutrient solution separation from air adds complexity)
 - pre-filtering necessary for handling of root material with possible microbial contamination and clogging issues
 - Porous plate nutrient delivery was selected against porous tube nutrient delivery to allow reutilization of the root module delivery system between growth cycles (the porous tube is captured by roots and needs to be replaced between growth cycles); reutilization of massive parts is a key target of a space greenhouse
 - Porous plate horizontal positioning was selected against vertical positioning to allow easier maintenance activities on the root module between growth cycles, as well as because the selected architecture favours air circulation through the root zone
 - One way nutrient delivery from nutrient stocks was selected against recirculating nutrient solution to reduce system complexity and fit with the envelope constraints
- Command and data handling system
 - NI LabVIEW was selected against Argus data acquisition system to permit for the possibility to maintain the developed code for a subsequent flight experiment when upgrading to a different National Instruments control board

2.4 Subsystem key values

The ISPR system key values are presented in the table below, divided into the most relevant ISPR subassemblies.

A margin of 20% has been added to the mass evaluation, since structural evaluation assessment is still under finalization.

A margin of 10% has been added to the power evaluation, since generally the equipment has all been selected, but the illumination panel performances are still to be confirmed by Heliospectra.

A margin of 30% is considered for cost evaluation, since multiple structural components are still to be defined and quoted accordingly.

Table 2-9: Key values of the ISPR system.

	Mass (kg)	Peak power (W)	Power day - nominal mode (W)	Power night - nominal mode (W)	Cost (k€)
Primary Structure	121.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6
Main Utilities Module	21.0	24.3	24.3	24.3	8
Upper Utilities Module	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	3
Power, C&DH Drawer	15.0	81.0	81.0	81.0	16
Nutrient Storage Drawer	23.0	40.4	40.4	40.4	21
Growth Chamber Drawer (Tall)	57.0	415.0	249.0	149.0	20
Growth Chamber Drawer (Short)	60.0	415.0	249.0	149.0	20
Illumination Drawer Left (Tall GC)	16.0	110.0	110.0	10.0	2.5
Illumination Drawer Right (Short GC)	16.0	110.0	110.0	10.0	2.5
TOTAL RACK (without margin)	332	1205	870	469	99
TOTAL RACK (with margins)	398	1325	957	516	128.7
Spares	146	-	-	-	15-20
TOTAL ISPR (with margins)	544	1325	957	516	114-149

3 Operations

The ISPR is designed to achieve an almost totally autonomous management of the various phase of growth of different plants. An operator is needed to perform the initialization of the system, the periodical substitution of the consumables, the harvesting and to fix eventual failures.

The following experiments are currently planned to be performed in the Antarctica test campaign:

- Growth Chamber Tall (GCT)
 - Dwarf Tomato: 3 growth experiments, 3 months each
- Growth Chamber Short (GCS)
 - Rucula (cultivated): 3 growth experiments, 1 month each
 - Chinese cabbage Tokyo Bekana: 3 growth experiments, 1 month each
 - Outredgeous lettuce: 3 growth experiments, 1 month each

The following subparagraphs provide a brief description of the main operations to be performed. A detailed procedure for each operation will be provided, but it is not within the scope of this document to provide it.

Operation ID is set as per following rule:

AAA_BBB_CCC_DDD			
AAA Values	BBB Values	CCC Values	DDD Values
NOM (Nominal)	AUT (automatic)	Drawer ID (GCS, GCT, ILR, ILL, PCD, NDS)	001, 002... 011... 00n
OFN (Off-nominal)	MAN (manual)	RCK (Full rack)	
MNT (Maintenance)	HYB (hybrid automatic and manual)		
SPM (Shipment)			

3.1 Nominal operations

In nominal operation, multiple automatic and operator-driven actions are defined as briefly outlined as follows.

In nominal operation, the operator shall initially check the state of the subsystems (aided and guided by the software). Then shall clean and setup both growth chambers in order to be ready for the plants growth (which consists in assembling inside the chamber the porous plates with the proper substrate blocks, connecting the tubes and the sensors from the Root Module to the chamber). When everything is ready, the cultivation software procedure shall be started, where some initial data shall be inserted (like the pH and EC of the bellow bags installed, the parameters of the plants which will be grown inside the chambers, etc.), and then the ISPR will enter an autonomous mode.

These operations shall be repeated by the operator about once a month for the GCS drawer and once every three months for the entire rack. This is preceded by the harvesting procedure, which foresee to stop the chamber interested, extract the plants grown and clean properly the empty chamber and all its subcomponents.

Periodically, the software will throw a warning concerning the depletion of one or more consumables (Water Tank; Flexible Bag A, B, Acid; CO₂ bottle): the operator shall be ready to accomplish the requests made by replacing or refill the empty tank asap (TBC 24h).

Multiple points must be taken into account for the purposes of general hygiene and to prevent and/or reduce the spread of disease and pests. These rules are collected in a dedicated document and apply to all entering the MTF where plant material from ISPR will be handled. A set of ISPR dedicated requirements was identified:

- The ISPR should be cleaned externally periodically with a sterilizing agent, and internally following each growth cycle.
- HW from storage and/or the cold porch should be properly cleaned prior to installation in the ISPR.

When handling plant material in the ISPR plastics gloves should be worn. When handling plant material from ISPR to be returned to it, the table surface and handling equipment should be cleaned (with a detergent to destroy any virus).

Table 10 reports the list of main nominal operations including operator actions.

Table 10: Main Nominal Operations (including operator actions) List

Operation ID	Descriptor	Frequency
NOM_HYB_RCK_001	System status check	After first power up
NOM_MAN_RCK_001	System cabling	Before first power up
NOM_MAN_NDS_001	Tank A, B filling	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_NDS_002	Tank A, B connection	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_NDS_003	Tank ACID connection	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_NDS_004	Tank H2O, NUT filling	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_NDS_005	Tank H2O, NUT connection	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_GCx_001	Growth chamber cleaning	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_GCx_002	Growth chamber experiment setup	Before first power up and before any new growth cycle
NOM_MAN_GCx_003	Growth chamber periodical inspection (base)	Every day during experiments
NOM_MAN_GCx_004	Growth chamber periodical inspection (advanced)	Once per week during experiments
NOM_MAN_GCS_005	Harvest of crop 1	Once per month (approx.)
NOM_MAN_GCS_006	Harvest of crop 2	Once per month (approx.)
NOM_MAN_GCS_007	Harvest of crop 3	Once per month (approx.)
NOM_MAN_GCT_008	Harvest of crop 4	Once every 3 months (approx.)

3.2 Off-Nominal operations

In case of contingency, multiple off-nominal operation have been identified, both automatic and operator-driven, as briefly outlined as follows.

Every time the power fails, the chamber is turned off, or a THC is replaced, the calibration of the Flux Deviators shall be repeated; this operation is aided by the software.

The software continuous test itself for problems or inconsistencies, and tries to recover autonomously the full functionality while sending a warning to the operator, who can decide (together with the Mission Control Center) to prepare to substitute the failed component.

In case the failure makes the normal operation unrecoverable, the ISPR will go in a partial Safe Mode, where the growth of the plants shall not be compromised, even if the perfect growing conditions may not be guaranteed.

In case of a major failure, the ISPR can enter a Critical Mode, where only the minimum conditions to avoid immediate death of the crops are maintained; the support of the operator is needed asap in order to recover the full operational condition.

3.3 Maintenance and spares

Maintenance (including consumables replacement) operations have been identified, all operator-driven, as briefly outlined as follows.

The complete list of spares is in the document in ANNEX 1 (to be provided).

Every three months, when the complete stop of the machine take place, the substitution of the HEPA-Carbon filters is foreseen: it can be achieved by removing the TCCS lines, opening them, cleaning them, change the filters, reassemble them and mounting them back to the chambers.

In case of a failure, a complete assembled THC is ready for replacement; the failed one shall then opened and the failed part substituted, in order to have back another fully functional THC ready for quick replacement.

3.4 Preparation for shipment

Prior to shipment, the NDS Drawer, the CO₂ bottles, the PCDH Drawer and the Root Modules shall be removed from the ISPR and stored properly (shocks, temperature, humidity) to avoid damaging and suffering through the travel. Removal need of all drawers in being investigated to reduce overall MTF mass during transport.

All the fluidic tubes and connections shall be emptied to avoid possible damage from freezing.

The remaining drawers (GCS, GCT, Illumination Left and Right, Storage) shall be properly secured to the rack in order to avoid unattended opening and/or detachment during the shipping.

4 Design lessons learned

The major design lessons learnt during subsystem testing phase are identified in the following subsections

4.1 Teflon bellows tank

Multiple (three) Teflon bellows prototype versions have been manufactured and tested, with incremental wall thickness. The major identified issue was related to the burst pressure, since burst was achieved at a lower level of proof pressure (1.5barg = 1.5xMDP) for both version 1 and 2. The initial HW was built upon suggestion of the bellows manufacturer, while a FE analysis would have already allowed identification of the criticality emerged during testing. The final version allowed reaching the maximum design pressure requirement, but the bellows free length was increased, thus requiring a slightly higher negative pressure (-0.07 barg) for emptying the tank. Reaching higher levels of design pressure (not currently the case for EDEN ISS) could be critical for the selected technology.

In addition, the installed electromagnetic stirrer final working point was selected after multiple iterations. The stirrer, designed to operate at 12 VDC, performs optimally at 4.5 VDC. At higher voltage the rotor speed is too high to properly initiate the motion of the magnetic stir bars within the bellows. The stirrer will then be operated at 4.5 VDC in the ISPR. However, further improvement would be allowing an incremental voltage provision, starting from even lower voltage.

Figure 32: Teflon bellows tank front/lateral view (left), back side view (centre), and internal view during stirrer operation (right)

4.2 Flexible concentrated nutrient solution reservoir

Multiple (three) Flexible concentrated nutrient solution reservoir prototype versions have been manufactured and tested, with incremental improvements. The major identified issue was related to the burst pressure, since burst was achieved at a lower level of proof pressure (1.5barg = 1.5xMDP) for both version 1 and 2. The first version revealed a weak point on the lateral bag welding where 3 bag foils converge into the same point. A dedicated welding tool was developed and the problem solved. A second weak point was then identified near the Teflon fitting holder. The fitting holder created a discontinuity with a slope too high to allow proper welding adhesion.

The third version of the bag reduces by a factor of 3 the fitting height and thus the discontinuity, allowing a much higher pressure load of the overall bag welding.

Figure 33: Soft reservoir lateral view (left), fitting view before proof test (centre), fitting view after proof test (right)

4.3 Porous nutrient delivery assembly

The ISPR porous nutrient delivery assembly in its final configuration is composed of the following elements: a water-proof bag (Figure 35) containing a capillary bag which encloses the root support substrate as per Figure 34. The capillary mat is put into contact with the inlet porous plate (Figure 35) through holes into the water proof layer, while no holes are needed in the bottom to allow water exit through the outlet porous plate (once the capillary layer is saturated water flows into the outlet plate).

Figure 34: Porous nutrient delivery assembly

Multiple configuration were tested prior to getting into this final layout:

- No water-proof bag around capillary bag: this solution was discarded because, although not losing water, it allows root material to grow out of the root block boundaries
- Water-proof bag with cut-out to place inlet porous plate in direct contact with capillary mat: this solution was discarded because, while allowing optimal wetting of the substrate, it was allowing water suction from the porous plate also when the pumps were off (with consequent loss of priming), as well as allowing root material to grow on the porous plate
- Water-proof bag with cut-out to place outlet porous plate in direct contact with capillary mat: this solution was discarded because of the same reasons reported in the point above, with the addition of excessive efficiency in draining the substrate (thus complete loss of internal priming)
- Water-proof bag with holes to place outlet porous plate partially in contact with capillary mat: this solution was discarded (at least for gravity applications), since the holes are not necessary for proper functioning of the substrate draining solution while creating a potential leak path in case of unexpected overwatering of the substrate while the suction pumps are off.

Figure 35: Porous plate (left) and water-proof bag not permeable to roots (right)

The best substrates for root module have been identified as perlite and zeolite, and both will be tested in Antarctica.

4.4 Ethylene passive regenerable scrubber

A passive filter (Figure 37) has been designed to allow scrubbing of ethylene from the growth chamber. The filter is placed into the TCCS segments as described in section 1.4. The filter is composed in its current version of a 3D-printed ABS-HI 40x40x100 mm case which encloses the ethylene adsorption material within two 10µm sintered stainless steel filters (mainly placed there to prevent adsorption material loss), as per Figure 36. The adsorption material is a Ceranovis patented coating applied to silica porous beads (Figure 37). The material is regenerable by exposure to heat above 90°C.

Figure 36: Ethylene scrubbing filter schematic

The currently major design lesson learnt is that the material is sensitive to high levels of relative humidity, so it should be stored with silica gel in a sealed bag before use.

The capacity of withholding ethylene is confirmed, however the following aspects are still to be determined via testing:

- exact correlation between ISPR greenhouse conditions and filter life-time (between regenerations)
- correlation of filter life-time against air relative humidity

Figure 37: Ethylene scrubbing filter photo (left) and adsorption material (right)

4.5 Quick disconnects for experimental insert fluidic lines

A sensible number of fluidic dripless QDs (in the order of 50) is part of the EDR2 insert/payload design. The typical flight qualified QDs (e.g. Parker, Walther Praezision) resulted too bulky, hard to operate within a limited access environment, as well as extremely expensive.

The now implemented solution relies on CPC water dripless acetate quick connects (see example in Figure 38) , which are compact, easy to operate, affordable and have been already used onboard the ISS in the NASA Veggie experiment. The extremely limited liquid leakage upon disconnection is acceptable for the current payload operation necessities.

Figure 38: CPC water dripless acetate quick connects

References

August 2004. NASA/CR—2004–208941. Advanced Life Support. Baseline Values and Assumptions Document. Anthony J. Hanford, Ph.D.

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